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ISSN (imprimé / *print*) : 1631-0683/ ISSN (électronique / *electronic*) : 1777-571X

Early Oligocene palaeoenvironment and palaeoclimate of the eastern periphery of the North Sea based on high-resolution palynological studies of the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole, northern Poland

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Submitted on 11 December 2023 | Accepted on 7 November 2024 | Published on 5 March 2025

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:5A48812A-6B21-4FA4-A207-A43A33C68F1B

Worobiec E., Gedl P., Worobiec G. & Granoszewski W. 2025. — Early Oligocene palaeoenvironment and palaeoclimate of the eastern periphery of the North Sea based on high-resolution palynological studies of the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole, northern Poland. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 24 (6): 67-87. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2025v24a6>

ABSTRACT

High-resolution palynological studies of the lower Oligocene strata from the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole from the eastern peripheries of the North Sea (Polish Gulf) revealed the presence of 165 fossil-species of sporomorphs (pollen grains and spores), numerous marine palynomorphs (e.g. dinoflagellate cysts), freshwater and brackish algae, plus fungal remains (including microsclerotia of dark septate endophytes inhabiting roots of plants). The composition of the palynological assemblage, including the fossil-species *Boeblensipollis hobli* Krutzsch and *Aglaoreidia cyclops* Erdtman, confirms the early Oligocene age of the strata. The presence of numerous dinoflagellate cysts throughout the Grabówka PIG-1 succession clearly indicates its deposition in a shallow marine, near-shore environment. The results of the spore-pollen analysis indicate the presence of lush vegetation with numerous thermophilous elements (including members of the pantropical families Meliaceae Jussieu and Sapotaceae Jussieu as well as the subtropical-tropical families Arecaceae Berchtold & J.Presl, Schizaeaceae Kaulfman, Cyatheaceae Kaulfman and/or Gleicheniaceae C.Presl) in the neighbouring land area. Mixed mesophytic forests, wetland (swamp or riparian) forests, shrub bogs, and freshwater/marsh vegetation dominated there. The climate was subtropical and humid. The entire palynological succession corresponds to the 5th Czempin group of lignite seams, correlated with the 5th Lusatian seam in south-eastern Germany, which is an important correlation horizon for the lower Oligocene in Central Europe. The results provide new insights into the vegetation and palaeoclimate changes in mid-latitudes during the early Oligocene greenhouse/icehouse transition.

KEY WORDS

Palynology,
pollen and spores,
non-pollen
palynomorphs,
fossil algae,
fossil fungi,
palaeogeography,
Europe,
Paleogene.

RÉSUMÉ

Paléoenvironnement et paléoclimat de l'Oligocène inférieur de la périphérie orientale de la mer du Nord, d'après des études palynologiques à haute résolution du forage Grabówka PIG-1, Nord de la Pologne.

Les études palynologiques à haute résolution des strates de l'Oligocène inférieur du forage Grabówka PIG-1 des périphéries orientales de la mer du Nord (golfe polonais) ont révélé la présence de 165 espèces fossiles de sporomorphes (grains de pollen et spores), de nombreux palynomorphes marins (par exemple des kystes de dinoflagellés), des algues d'eaux douces et saumâtres, ainsi que des restes fongiques (y compris des microsclérotés endophytes bruns septés des racines des plantes). La composition de l'assemblage palynologique, comprenant les espèces fossiles *Boehlensipollis hobli* Krutzsch et *Aglaoreidia cyclops* Erdtman, confirme l'âge Oligocène inférieur des strates. La présence de nombreux kystes de dinoflagellés tout au long de la succession Grabówka PIG-1 indique clairement son dépôt dans un environnement marin peu profond, proche du rivage. Les résultats de l'analyse sporo-pollinique indiquent la présence d'une végétation luxuriante avec de nombreux éléments thermophiles (y compris des membres des familles pantropicales Meliaceae Jussieu et Sapotaceae Jussieu ainsi que les familles subtropicales-tropicales Arecaceae Berchtold & J.Presl, Schizaeaceae Kaulfman, Cyatheaceae Kaulfman et/ou Gleicheniaceae C.Presl) dans les terres voisines. Les forêts mésophytiques mixtes, les forêts de zones humides (marécageuses ou riveraines), les tourbières arbustives et la végétation d'eau douce/marais dominaient. Le climat était subtropical et humide. L'ensemble de la succession palynologique correspond à la 5^e couche de lignite de Czempin, corrélée à la 5^e couche de Lusace dans le Sud-Est de l'Allemagne, qui constitue un horizon de corrélation important pour l'Oligocène inférieur en Europe centrale. Les résultats fournissent de nouvelles informations sur la végétation et les changements paléoclimatiques des latitudes moyennes au cours de la transition «greenhouse/icehouse» de l'Oligocène inférieur.

MOTS CLÉS

Palynologie,
pollen et spores,
palynomorphes non
polliniques,
algues fossiles,
champignons fossiles,
paléogéographie,
Europe,
Paléogène.

INTRODUCTION

The Eocene-Oligocene transition was a period of dynamic changes in the Earth's climate and ecosystems presumed to be the most prominent one in the Cenozoic (e.g. Hutchinson *et al.* 2021). It is widely accepted that at that time (about 33.7 million years ago) an abrupt cooling occurred near that boundary (e.g. Shackleton & Kennett 1975; Kennett & Shackleton 1976; Kennett 1977; Pomerol & Premoli Silva 1986; Coxall & Pearson 2007; Liu *et al.* 2009). Climate change was very rapid and that shift lasted, depending on the author, from 500 000 years to some 790 000 years only (e.g. Coxall & Pearson 2007; Hutchinson *et al.* 2021). At that time, polar ice caps, absent during the Eocene and Paleocene (the time when ice sheets were missing is commonly known as the “greenhouse”), appeared (e.g. Coxall & Wilson 2011), and the early Oligocene is believed to represent the beginning of the modern “icehouse” world (i.e., time with polar glaciations present, starting from the Eocene-Oligocene transition till Recent), in which Earth's ecosystems adapted to cooling climatic conditions following the preceding late Eocene thermal maximum (Zachos *et al.* 2001, 2008; Li *et al.* 2018; Westerhold *et al.* 2020). Among the reasons cited as responsible for these climatic changes across the Eocene-Oligocene boundary, atmospheric CO₂ reduction seems to have the greatest impact, while the emergence of polar ice caps and changes in ocean current patterns induced by sea-floor tectonics seem to have a lesser impact (e.g. Hutchinson *et al.* 2021). However, a precise scenario of climatic fluctuations and their extent during the transitional interval as well as in the subsequent times of the younger Oligocene times

is still a matter of debate. Moreover, some data suggest less climatic cooling during the Oligocene than one might suppose from the word “icehouse” (e.g. O'Brien *et al.* 2020). To add some data to that issue we conducted a high-resolution palynological research on a lower Oligocene littoral section from the eastern periphery (Polish Gulf; Śliwińska *et al.* 2019) of the North Sea (northern Poland) that represents an age-counterpart of brackish-lacustrine sediments with lignite interlayers (the so-called Czempin Formation) widespread in the Polish Lowland basin (Piwocki 2004). The mass accumulation of phytogenic deposits of that time, known as the 5th Czempin group of lignite seams, reflected specific climatic and orographic conditions that have appeared in the Polish Lowland basin for the first time then. Subsequent periods of increased phytogenic accumulation, repeated regularly during the Miocene in the Polish Lowlands and adjacent areas, likely reflect optimal conditions for lush vegetation, which can be correlated with climatic fluctuations that occurred in the Miocene (see e.g. Kürschner *et al.* 2008).

The accumulation of phytogenic deposits of the 5th group of lignite seams reflected thus specific climatic conditions that had appeared for the first time during the early Oligocene, i.e., in the period traditionally regarded as “icehouse” cold time. To clarify these ambiguities, we conducted a palynological study of the 5.6-metre-thick succession from the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole. Although the lower Oligocene strata have been palynologically studied for years from relatively numerous sections in the Polish Lowlands (Grabowska & Piwocki 1975; Grabowska & Słodkowska 1993; Grabowska 1996b; Słodkowska 2004a, b, 2009; Kasiński & Słodkowska 2016), most of these studies are contributory only or are based on

FIG. 1. — Location maps of the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole: **A**, general location; **B**, location of the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole in Poland and geographical extent of the Oligocene basin (according to Vinken 1988; Widera & Kita 2007) and the 5th Czempień lignite seam group (simplified, after Kasiński & Słodkowska 2016; supplemented by Gedl *et al.* 2016; Worobiec & Szulc 2020). Lower Oligocene localities mentioned in the text: 1, Pomeranian Lakeland area; 2, Warmia and Mazury; 3, Warszce 19 borehole, Rogóżno deposit; 4, Middle Vistula River valley; 5, Łukowa-4 borehole; 6, Górażdże.

very scarce material. The results and interpretations of our high-resolution (sampling every 10 cm) terrestrial palynological study (including spore-pollen, freshwater algae and fungal analysis) combined with the results of preliminary studies on marine dinoflagellate cysts provide new insights into climatic conditions during this interesting and dynamically changing period.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The study area is located in northern Poland (Fig. 1) in the Lower Vistula Valley. The riverbed of the Vistula (Wisła) river in this area is covered by Holocene river sands and gravel, which cut the upper parts of the plateau formed by the Pleistocene (Vistulian) moraines (Kozłowska & Kozłowski 1984). The Quaternary deposits in the study area are over 80 m thick and consist of glacial deposits of the Narew (MIS 22), San 2 (MIS 12), Odra (MIS 6), and Vistula glaciations (MIS 4-2) (Lisicki 2010). These strata rest directly upon Paleogene sediments (Neogene is missing in the study area), which start at the depth of 82.4 m in the Grabówka PIG-1 (Grabówka-2) well. The interval 82.4-88.0 m studied from the Grabówka PIG-1 well represents the so-called Czempień Formation, a part of the Paleogene succession of the Polish Lowlands, which accumulated in the north-eastern peripheries of the NW European Tertiary Basin.

Lithostratigraphy of the Polish Lowlands' Paleogene succession has an informal character being composed of several units in the ranks of beds, series or formations; their defini-

Epoch	Stage	Lithostratigraphic scheme of the Polish Lowlands
OLIGOCENE	CHATTIAN	Leszno Formation
	RUPELIAN	Upper Mosina Formation
Rupel Formation		Czempień Formation
EOCENE		Lower Mosina Formation

FIG. 2. — Lithostratigraphic scheme of the Oligocene in the Polish Lowlands (after Piwocki 2004).

tions, correlations and age assessments changed throughout the years – in this paper we use the lithostratigraphic scheme (Fig. 2) proposed and discussed by Piwocki (2004). The oldest Oligocene unit in the Polish Lowlands is the Lower Mosina Formation which rest unconformably on the upper Eocene series. These are marine quartz-glaucconite sands, usually fine-grained, locally loamy or with admixtures of quartz gravels, with phosphorite concretions in the basal intervals.

The spatial distribution of this unit is the widest among the Oligocene ones in the Polish Lowlands; it covers an area similar to that of the entire Oligocene. Younger units show more local occurrence. The Lower Mosina Formation passes upwards in the north-western part of the Polish Lowlands into the Rupel Formation, which is also marine but finer-grained than the underlying strata; in the Rupel Formation mud and clay fractions predominate.

The Czempiń Formation, which is the subject of our study in the Grabówka PIG-1 well, is another Rupelian unit widespread in the Polish Lowlands. In contrast to the above-described units, these strata accumulated during the regressive phase of the early Oligocene in continental (swampy-lacustrine) and brackish (littoral, tidal, lagoonal, estuarine) sedimentary settings. This unit is composed mainly of dark-coloured mud and fine-grained sands with a high proportion of lignite, locally forming lignite seams (known as the 5th Czempiń group of lignite seams, see below). The youngest Rupelian unit in the Polish Lowlands is the Upper Mosina Formation, which transgressively overlies the older units. These are marine, mainly sandy deposits (quartz-glaucinite, fine-grained sands with variable admixture of finer mud fraction) with characteristic gravel and phosphorite concretion layers at the base. The Upper Mosina Formation terminates the accumulation of Paleogene strata on an overwhelming part of the Polish Lowlands: during the latest Rupelian-earliest Chattian, the sea withdrew from these territories except for a small marine bay that existed during the Chattian in south-western Poland.

Transgression/regression oscillations from the North Sea during the early Oligocene caused vertical and lateral facies variations, which slightly obscure the simplified scheme given above (Piwocki 2004). The coastline of the basin cannot be precisely defined due to facies interfingering and subsequent erosion that removed large portions of the Paleogene cover. Nevertheless, the lithology and the thickness of these deposits suggest that the epicontinental sea connected to the North Sea extended further south than the present towns of Konin and Turek. The central-western Poland formed a southern marginal part of this basin (Widera & Kita 2007). The Rupelian marine and brackish deposits are most frequently synchronous with brackish-lacustrine sediments containing lignite interbeds of the 5th Czempiń lignite seam group (Piwocki 2004). The 5th lignite seam has a limited extent and it has been documented across an area of *c.* 7700 km², mainly in North-Western Poland (Fig. 1). Its thickness is usually small, not exceeding 1 m, although it reaches a considerable thickness in depressions in the salt dome caps. In extreme cases (e.g. in the Rogóżno and Wapno salt domes), its thickness may exceed 40 m (Kasiński & Słodkowska 2016). The Czempiń Formation corresponds to the so-called Septarian Clays of Germany (Piwocki 2004) and the Czempiń seam is correlated with the 5th Lusatian Seam in the south-eastern territory of Germany (Widera 2016). Palynological studies of the 5th group of lignite seams are used in a regional or interregional correlation of the lower Oligocene strata in a parastratigraphic sense (Vinken 1988; Widera & Kita 2007).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

MATERIAL

The Grabówka PIG-1 (Grabówka-2) borehole was drilled in July 2008 as a research well of the Middle Pleistocene strata. The borehole was located in the Kwidzyn Valley (Dolina Kwidzyńska) in the village of Grabówko (53°42'40"N, 18°50'30"E; Fig. 1), about 6 km south-east of the city of Kwidzyn, at an altitude of 14.5 m a.s.l., and reached a depth of 126 m (Lisicki 2010). The top 9.3 m of the well are Holocene fluvial deposits, below which almost 80 metres of Pleistocene glacial deposits occur. At the depth of 82.4–88.0 m a loamy to very fine-grained sandy interval with lignite occurs. This core fragment, thought to be a facies counterpart of the 5th group of lignite seams is the subject of the present study. Below, an unsampled interval composed of coarse-grained marine sands (88–95 m) and mudstones with chert concretions and fragments of mollusc shells (104.5–126.0 m) occurs. The results of petrographic and palynological studies of the Pleistocene from the Grabówka PIG-1 succession were compiled by Lisicki (2010), while the Paleogene part (based on material additionally collected during the Pleistocene studies) has not been investigated yet and is presented for the first time in this paper.

PREPARATION METHODS AND PALYNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

A total of 55 samples were collected from the Grabówka PIG-1 core interval of 87.8–82.4 m (with a sampling density of every 10 cm) for palynological studies including classical spore-pollen analysis and recognition of the presence of non-pollen palynomorphs (NPPs; such as freshwater algae, prasinophytes, acritarchs, dinoflagellate cysts, and fungal remains). The samples were processed in the Laboratory of the W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, using successively 10% hydrochloric acid (HCl), 10% potassium hydroxide (KOH), 40% hydrofluoric acid (HF) for four days to remove silicates (HF was heated at the beginning of the treatment), and subsequently 10% hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Moore *et al.* 1991; Worobiec *et al.* 2021). The residuum was then sieved at 5 µm on a nylon mesh. From each sample 1–2 (max. 8) microscope slides were made, using glycerine jelly or glycerine as a mounting medium.

Additionally, eleven samples from an interval of 87.80–82.80 m (sampling density every 50 cm, i.e., every fifth sample of these taken for spore-pollen analysis) were taken for organic-walled dinoflagellate cysts and processed separately. They were prepared at the Institute of Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences, Research Centre in Kraków. The samples were subjected to the processing procedure, which included 38% hydrochloric acid (HCl) treatment, 40% hydrofluoric acid (HF) treatment, heavy-liquid (ZnCl₂+HCl; density 2.0 g·cm⁻³) separation, ultrasound for 10–15 s and sieving at 10 µm on a nylon mesh. No nitric acid (HNO₃) treatment was applied. The quantity of each rock sample processed was 20 g. Two slides from each sample were made using glycerine jelly as a mounting medium.

FIG. 3. — Spores of plants and pollen grains from Grabówka PIG-1: **A**, *Stereisporites stereoides* (Potonié & Venitz) Thomson & Pflug, 1953; **B**, **C**, *Camarozonosporites heskemensis* (Pflanzl) Krutzsch, 1959, same specimen, various foci; **D**, **E**, *Retitriletes annotinioides* Krutzsch, 1963, same specimen, various foci; **F**, *Leiotriletes cf. neddenioides* Krutzsch, 1962; **G**, *Sequoiapollenites rugulus* Krutzsch, 1971; **H**, *Sequoiapollenites megaligulus* Krutzsch, 1971; **I**, *Cupressacites* sp.; **J**, *Inaperturopollenites dubius* (Potonié & Venitz) Thomson & Pflug, 1953; **K**, *Pinuspollenites labdacus* (Potonié) Raatz ex Potonié, 1958; **L**, *Cathayapollis krutzschii* (Sivak) Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 2002; **M**, *Zonalapollenites* sp.; **N**, *Sciadopityspollenites serratus* (Potonié & Venitz) Raatz ex Potonié, 1958; **O**, *Sciadopityspollenites* sp.; **P**, **Q**, *Sciadopityspollenites quintus* Krutzsch ex Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 1974, same specimen, various foci. Scale bar: 10 μ m.

The sporomorph taxa identified were classified based on the *Atlas of Pollen and Spores of the Polish Neogene* (Stuchlik *et al.* 2001, 2002, 2009, 2014). In the material studied, the following palaeofloristical (and palaeoclimatic) elements were distinguished: “palaeotropical” (P), including “tropical” (P1) and “subtropical” (P2), “arctotertiary” (A), including “warm-temperate” (A1) and “temperate” (A2), as well as cosmopolitan (P/A). Data from the palynological spectra were used to construct a simplified palynological diagram. In the diagram, the percentages of pollen and spore taxa were calculated from the total sum of pollen grains and spores; the proportions of non-pollen palynomorphs (NPPs) were computed separately from the total sum using the POLPAL computer programme (Nalepka & Walanus 2003). Photomicrographs of selected (the most important and characteristic) palynomorphs (Figs 3-5) were taken using a Nikon Eclipse E400 microscope, fitted with a Canon A640 digital camera.

PALAEOCLIMATE RECONSTRUCTION

The palaeoclimatic considerations presented in this paper are limited to general estimations, including the mean annual temperatures (MAT), as such data from marine sediments should be treated with caution. These MAT estimates are based on the Coexistence Approach (CA) method (Utescher *et al.* 2014), which basic assumption is that the nearest living relatives (NLR) of fossil taxa provide the information necessary to find a climatic distribution interval, where all plants could live (Coexistence Interval). The CA uses only the presence or absence of the taxa, without considering their relative frequency. The nearest living relatives and their MAT ranges follow The Palaeoflora Database (Utescher & Mosbrugger 2015; Utescher *et al.* 2024). For the CA method, the authors selected as many taxa as possible (Table 3) excluding fossil taxa with unknown botanical affinity, related to families, aquatic taxa, etc. Considering the limitations of the CA method (Utescher *et al.* 2014), e.g. the problem of determining the NLR of some fossil taxa (Kvaček 2007) and the fact that the difference between fossil and NLR increases with time distance, we only estimated the general MAT range for the palynoflora. We also excluded the species producing bisaccate pollen grains from this consideration, as they are exceptionally well adapted to long-distance transport.

ABBREVIATIONS

Institutional abbreviations

PIG Polish Geological Institute, Warszawa.

Other abbreviations

A “arctotertiary” palaeofloristical element;
 A1 “warm-temperate” palaeofloristical element;
 A2 “temperate” palaeofloristical element;
 CA Coexistence Approach;
 DSE dark septate endophytes;
 MAT mean annual temperature;
 NLR nearest living relatives;
 NPP non-pollen palynomorphs;
 P “palaeotropical” palaeofloristical element;
 P1 “tropical” palaeofloristical element;
 P2 “subtropical” palaeofloristical element;
 P/A cosmopolitan palaeofloristical element.

RESULTS OF THE PALYNOLOGICAL STUDIES

All samples processed yielded rich palynological organic matter, but the uppermost sample (depth 82.4 m) yielded material mixed with younger, probably Pleistocene palynomorphs (this sample was collected at the contact between the Paleogene and Pleistocene); therefore we excluded this sample from further consideration.

SPORE-POLLEN ANALYSIS

The lowermost sample (depth 87.80 m) processed for pollen and spores yielded very few palynomorphs. The same sample treated with heavy liquid during processing (see chapter Material and methods) provided some dinoflagellate cysts. The remaining 53 samples (depth interval 87.7-82.5 m) gave well-preserved pollen grains and spores, suitable for detailed palynological analysis (Figs 3-5). In these samples, at least 500 pollen grains and spores of plants were identified as well as all co-occurring NPP were counted. The pollen grains of gymnosperms (Figs 3G-Q; 4A) are dominant in all samples, but angiosperms (Figs 4B-FF; 5A-M) are represented by many more taxa (mainly from trees and shrubs); plant spores (Fig. 3A-F) are few. A total of 165 fossil-species of sporomorphs (including 33 species of gymnosperm pollen, 108 species of angiosperm pollen, and 24 species of plant spores) were identified (Table 1). “Palaeotropical” (including “tropical” and “subtropical”) and “palaeotropical/warm-temperate” palaeofloristical elements are common in the palynoflora (Table 1). The proportions of taxa representing various palaeofloristical elements are similar throughout the diagram (Fig. 6).

Among the gymnosperms, pollen grains of Pinaceae (mainly fossil-genus *Pinuspollenites* Raatz ex Potonié, 1958) and Cupressaceae (with distinct papillae and others) as well as some *Sciadopityspollenites* Raatz ex Potonié, 1958 are dominant. Pollen of *Distachyapites* (Krutzschn Grabowska, 2002, related to the *Ephedra* genus, were encountered in five samples (depth 87.5 m, 87.0 m, 86.9 m, 84.3 m, 84.1 m). Angiosperms are represented mainly by small tricolporate pollen grains from the Fagaceae family (mainly fossil-species *Fususpollenites fusus* (Potonié) Kedves, 1978, *Cupuliferopollenites pusillus* (Potonié) Potonié ex Potonié, 1960, and *Quercoidites microhenricii* (Potonié) Potonié, Thomson & Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960) as well as *Platanipollis ipelensis* (Pacltová) Grabowska, 1994, *Myricipites* Wodehouse emend. Grabowska & Ważyńska, 2009, *Cyrillaceapollenites* (Mürriger & Pflug) Potonié, 1960, *Ericipites* Wodehouse, 1933, *Tricolporopollenites dolium* (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953, *Tricolporopollenites villensis* (Thomson) Thomson & Pflug, 1953, *Nyssapollenites* Thiergart, 1938, *Ilexpollenites* Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960, *Alnipollenites* Potonié emend. Grabowska & Ważyńska, 2009, members of the families Hamamelidaceae (fossil-species *Corylopsispollenites microreticulatus* E. Worobiec, 2014 and *Tricolporopollenites stavesedloensis* Krutzschn & Pacltová, 1969), Sapotaceae, Juglandaceae (mainly members of the fossil-genera *Momipites* Wodehouse emend. Nichols, 1973, *Caryapollenites* Raatz

TABLE 1. — Spores and pollen taxa, recorded in samples from the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole. Taxonomy, botanical affinity and palaeofloristical elements according to Stuchlik *et al.* (2001, 2002, 2009, 2014). The following palaeofloristical elements have been distinguished: “palaeotropical” (P), including “tropical” (P1) and “subtropical” (P2), and “arctotertiary” (A), including “warm-temperate” (A1) and “temperate” (A2), as well as cosmopolitan (P/A).

Fossil taxon	Botanical affinity	Element
Spores of plants:		
<i>Baculatisporites primarius</i> (Wolff) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Osmundaceae: <i>Osmunda</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Baculatisporites</i> sp.	Osmundaceae: <i>Osmunda</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Camarozonosporites heskemensis</i> (Pflanzl) Krutzsch, 1959	Lycopodiaceae: <i>Lycopodiella</i> Holub, 1964	P
<i>Camarozonosporites</i> sp.	Lycopodiaceae: <i>Lycopodiella</i> Holub, 1964	P
<i>Cicatricosporites dorogensis</i> Potonié & Gelletich, 1933	Schizaeaceae	P
<i>Corrugatisporites</i> sp.	Lygodiaceae	P2
<i>Distancoraesporis</i> sp.	Sphagnaceae: <i>Sphagnum</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Laevigatosporites haardti</i> (Potonié & Venitz) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Polypodiaceae, Davalliaceae, and other ferns	P/A
<i>Laevigatosporites</i> sp.	Polypodiaceae, Davalliaceae, and other ferns	P/A
<i>Leiotriletes maxoides</i> Krutzsch, 1962	Lygodiaceae	P
<i>Leiotriletes neddenioides</i> Krutzsch, 1962	Lygodiaceae?, Cyatheaceae?	P
<i>Leiotriletes wolffii</i> Krutzsch, 1962	Lygodiaceae	P
<i>Leiotriletes</i> sp.	Lygodiaceae and other ferns	P
<i>Monoleiotriletes</i> sp.	ferns	unknown
<i>Neogenisporis neogenicus</i> Krutzsch, 1962	p.p. Gleicheniaceae	P1
<i>Neogenisporis</i> sp.	Gleicheniaceae, Cyatheaceae	P1
<i>Polypodiaceoisporites</i> sp.	Schizaeaceae?, Dicksoniaceae?, Pteridaceae?, Cyatheaceae?	P/A1
<i>Retitriletes annotinioides</i> Krutzsch, 1963	Lycopodiaceae: <i>Lycopodium</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Retitriletes lusaticus</i> Krutzsch, 1963	Lycopodiaceae: <i>Lycopodium</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Retitriletes</i> sp.	Lycopodiaceae: <i>Lycopodium</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Stereisporites stereoides</i> (Potonié & Venitz) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Sphagnaceae: <i>Sphagnum</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Stereisporites</i> sp.	Sphagnaceae: <i>Sphagnum</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Triplanosporites</i> sp.	unknown	P
<i>Verrucatosporites</i> sp.	Davalliaceae, Polypodiaceae, and other ferns	P/A
Pollen grains of gymnosperms:		
<i>Abiespollenites</i> sp.	Pinaceae: <i>Abies</i> Miller, 1768	A
<i>Cathayapollis erdtmanii</i> (Sivak) Ziembińska-Tworzydło <i>in</i> Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> 2002	Pinaceae: <i>Cathaya</i> Chun & Kuang, 1962	A1
<i>Cathayapollis krutzschii</i> (Sivak) Ziembińska-Tworzydło <i>in</i> Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Pinaceae: <i>Cathaya</i> Chun & Kuang, 1962	A1
<i>Cathayapollis</i> cf. <i>pulaensis</i> (Nagy) Ziembińska-Tworzydło <i>in</i> Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Pinaceae: <i>Cathaya</i> Chun & Kuang, 1962	A1
<i>Cathayapollis</i> sp.	Pinaceae: <i>Cathaya</i> Chun & Kuang, 1962	A1
<i>Cedripites</i> sp.	Pinaceae: <i>Cedrus</i> Trew, 1755	A1
<i>Cunninghamiaepollenites</i> sp.	Cupressaceae: <i>Cunninghamia</i> R. Brown <i>in</i> L. C. Richard, 1826	A1
<i>Cupressacites</i> sp.	Cupressaceae	A1
<i>Distachyapites eocenicus</i> (Wodehouse) Grabowska & Ważyńska <i>in</i> Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Ephedraceae: <i>Ephedra</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Distachyapites</i> sp.	Ephedraceae: <i>Ephedra</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Inaperturopollenites concedipites</i> (Wodehouse) Krutzsch, 1971	Cupressaceae: <i>Taxodium</i> Richard, 1810, <i>Glyptostrobus</i> Endlicher, 1847	P2/A1
<i>Inaperturopollenites dubius</i> (Potonié & Venitz) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Cupressaceae: <i>Taxodium</i> Richard, 1810, <i>Glyptostrobus</i> Endlicher, 1847	P2/A1
<i>Inaperturopollenites verrupilatus</i> Trevisan, 1967	Cupressaceae: <i>Taxodium</i> Richard, 1810, <i>Glyptostrobus</i> Endlicher, 1847	P2/A1
<i>Keteleeriapollenites dubius</i> (Khlonova) Słodkowska <i>in</i> Ziembińska-Tworzydło <i>et al.</i> , 1994	Pinaceae: <i>Keteleeria</i> Carrière, 1866	A1
<i>Piceapollenites alatus</i> Potonié ex Potonié, 1958	Pinaceae	P/A
<i>Piceapollis planoides</i> Krutzsch ex Hochuli, 1978	Pinaceae: <i>Picea</i> Dietrich, 1824	A
<i>Piceapollis</i> sp.	Pinaceae: <i>Picea</i> Dietrich, 1824	A
<i>Pinuspollenites labdacus</i> (Potonié) Raatz ex Potonié, 1958	Pinaceae: <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> Linnaeus, 1753 type	A
<i>Pinuspollenites</i> sp.	Pinaceae: <i>Pinus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Sciadopityspollenites antiquus</i> Krutzsch ex Planderová, 1990	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sciadopityspollenites miniverrucatus</i> Kohlman-Adamska <i>in</i> Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sciadopityspollenites quintus</i> Krutzsch ex Ziembińska-Tworzydło, 1974	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sciadopityspollenites serratus</i> (Potonié & Venitz) Raatz ex Potonié, 1958	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sciadopityspollenites varius</i> Krutzsch ex Ziembińska-Tworzydło, 1974	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sciadopityspollenites verticillatiformis</i> (Zauer) Krutzsch, 1971	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sciadopityspollenites</i> sp.	Sciadopityaceae: <i>Sciadopitys</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1842	A1
<i>Sequoiapollenites gracilis</i> Krutzsch, 1971	Cupressaceae: <i>Sequoia</i> Endlicher, 1847, <i>Sequoiadendron</i> Buchholz, 1939, <i>Metasequoia</i> Hu & Cheng, 1948, <i>Cryptomeria</i> Don, 1838	A1

Table 1. — Continuation.

Fossil taxon	Botanical affinity	Element
<i>Sequoiapollenites major</i> Krutzsch, 1971	Cupressaceae: <i>Sequoia</i> Endlicher, 1847, <i>Sequoiadendron</i> Buchholz, 1939, <i>Metasequoia</i> Hu & Cheng, 1948, <i>Cryptomeria</i> Don, 1838	A1
<i>Sequoiapollenites megaligulus</i> Krutzsch, 1971	Cupressaceae, incl. <i>Sequoiadendron</i> Buchholz, 1939	A1
<i>Sequoiapollenites rugulus</i> Krutzsch, 1971	Cupressaceae: <i>Sequoia</i> Endlicher, 1847, <i>Sequoiadendron</i> Buchholz, 1939, <i>Metasequoia</i> Hu & Cheng, 1948	A1
<i>Sequoiapollenites</i> sp.	Cupressaceae: <i>Sequoia</i> Endlicher, 1847, <i>Sequoiadendron</i> Buchholz, 1939, <i>Metasequoia</i> Hu & Cheng, 1948, <i>Cryptomeria</i> Don, 1838	A1
<i>Zonalapollenites verrucatus</i> Krutzsch ex Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 1974	Pinaceae: <i>Tsuga</i> (Endlicher) Carrière, 1855	A
<i>Zonalapollenites</i> sp.	Pinaceae: <i>Tsuga</i> (Endlicher) Carrière, 1855	A
Pollen grains of angiosperms:		
<i>Aceripollenites striatus</i> (Pflug) Thiele-Pfeiffer, 1980	Sapindaceae: <i>Acer</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A1
<i>Aceripollenites</i> sp.	Sapindaceae: <i>Acer</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Aglaoreidia cyclops</i> Erdtman, 1960	Sparganiaceae?, Potamogetonaceae?, Ruppiaceae?	P
<i>Alnipollenites metaplasma</i> (Potonié) Potonié, 1960	Betulaceae: <i>Alnus</i> Miller, 1754	A
<i>Alnipollenites verus</i> Potonié, 1931	Betulaceae: <i>Alnus</i> Miller, 1754	P2/A
<i>Araliaceopollenites euphorii</i> (Potonié) Potonié ex Potonié, 1960	Araliaceae	P/A1
<i>Araliaceopollenites</i> sp.	Araliaceae	P/A1
<i>Arecipites convexus</i> (Thiergart) Krutzsch, 1970	Arecaceae	P/A1
<i>Arecipites minireticulatus</i> Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło in Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Arecaceae	P/A1
<i>Arecipites pseudoconvexus</i> Krutzsch, 1970	Amaryllidaceae, Araceae, Arecaceae	P2/A1
<i>Arecipites</i> sp.	Araceae, Arecaceae, Butomaceae	P/A
<i>Boehlensipollis hohli</i> Krutzsch, 1962	Elaeagnaceae?, Lythraceae?	P2/A1
<i>Caprifoliipites viburnoides</i> (Gruas-Cavagnetto) Kohlman-Adamska in Ziemińska-Tworzydło <i>et al.</i> , 1994	Adoxaceae: <i>Viburnum</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Caprifoliipites</i> sp.	Adoxaceae: <i>Sambucus</i> Linnaeus, 1753, <i>Viburnum</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Carpinipites carpinoides</i> (Pflug) Nagy, 1985	Betulaceae: <i>Carpinus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Caryapollenites simplex</i> (Potonié) Raatz ex Potonié, 1960	Juglandaceae: <i>Carya</i> Nuttall, 1818	A1
<i>Caryapollenites triangulus</i> (Pflug) Krutzsch, 1961	Juglandaceae: <i>Carya</i> Nuttall, 1818	P
<i>Celtipollenites</i> sp.	Ulmaceae: <i>Celtis</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Cercidiphyllites minimireticulatus</i> (Trevisan) Ziemińska-Tworzydło in Ziemińska-Tworzydło <i>et al.</i> , 1994	Cercidiphyllaceae: <i>Cercidiphyllum</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1846	A1
<i>Chenopodipollis</i> sp.	Amaranthaceae (incl. Chenopodiaceae)	P/A
<i>Cornaceaeapollis major</i> (Stuchlik) Stuchlik ex Jansonius <i>et al.</i> , 1998	Cornaceae: <i>Cornus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Cornaceaeapollis satzveyensis</i> (Pflug) Ziemińska-Tworzydło ex Jansonius <i>et al.</i> , 1998	Mastixiaceae: <i>Mastixia</i> Blume, 1826	P1
<i>Cornaceaeapollis</i> sp.	Cornaceae: <i>Cornus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A
<i>Corsinipollenites</i> sp.	Onagraceae	P/A
<i>Corylopsispollenites microreticulatus</i> E. Worobiec in Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Hamamelidaceae: <i>Corylopsis</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1835	A1
<i>Cupanieidites eucalyptoides</i> Krutzsch, 1962	Myrtaceae?, Sapindaceae?	P/A1
<i>Cupuliferoipollenites oviformis</i> (Potonié) Potonié ex Potonié, 1960	Fagaceae: Castaneoideae: <i>Castanea</i> Miller, 1754, <i>Castanopsis</i> (Don) Spach, 1841, <i>Lithocarpus</i> Blume, 1826	P2/A1
<i>Cupuliferoipollenites pusillus</i> (Potonié) Potonié ex Potonié, 1960	Fagaceae: Castaneoideae: <i>Castanea</i> Miller, 1754, <i>Castanopsis</i> (Don) Spach, 1841, <i>Lithocarpus</i> Blume, 1826	P2/A1
<i>Cyperaceaeapollis neogenicus</i> Krutzsch, 1970	Cyperaceae	P/A
<i>Cyrrillaceaeapollenites brühlensis</i> (Thomson) Durska in Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Cyrrillaceae, Clethraceae	P
<i>Cyrrillaceaeapollenites exactus</i> (Potonié) Potonié, 1960	Cyrrillaceae, Clethraceae	P
<i>Cyrrillaceaeapollenites megaexactus</i> (Potonié) Potonié, 1960	Cyrrillaceae, Clethraceae	P
<i>Dicolpopollis</i> sp.	Arecaceae	P
<i>Dicolporopollis middendorffii</i> (Potonié) Krutzsch, 1961	unknown	unknown
<i>Edmundipollis</i> sp.	Cornaceae, Mastixiaceae, Araliaceae	P/A
<i>Ericipites callidus</i> (Potonié) Krutzsch, 1970	Ericaceae	A
<i>Ericipites ericius</i> (Potonié) Potonié, 1960	Ericaceae	A
<i>Ericipites triangulus</i> Grabowska in Stuchlik <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Ericaceae	A
<i>Ericipites</i> sp.	Ericaceae	A
<i>Faguspollenites</i> sp.	Fagaceae: <i>Fagus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Fraxinipollis</i> sp.	Oleaceae: <i>Fraxinus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Fususpollenites fusus</i> (Potonié) Kedves, 1978	Fagaceae: <i>Trigonobalanus</i> Forman, 1962 s.l. (incl. <i>Colombobalanus</i> Nixon & Crepet, 1989)	P1
<i>Graminidites</i> sp.	Poaceae: Pooideae	P/A
<i>Ilexpollenites iliacus</i> (Potonié) Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	Aquifoliaceae: <i>Ilex</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Ilexpollenites margaritatus</i> (Potonié) Thiergart, 1938	Aquifoliaceae: <i>Ilex</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2
<i>Intratrisporopollenites insculptus</i> Mai, 1961	Malvaceae: Brownlowioideae, Tilioideae	P/A1

Table 1. — Continuation.

Fossil taxon	Botanical affinity	Element
<i>Intratropipollenites</i> sp.	Malvaceae: Brownlowioideae, Tilioideae	P/A
<i>Juglanspollenites</i> sp.	Juglandaceae: <i>Juglans</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A1
<i>Magnoliaepollenites</i> sp.	Magnoliaceae: <i>Magnolia</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Meliaceoidites</i> sp.	Meliaceae	P
<i>Milfordia hypolaenoides</i> Erdtman, 1960	Restionaceae, Centrolepidaceae	P
<i>Milfordia miocaenica</i> Grabowska & Słodkowska in Stuchlik et al., 2009	Restionaceae, Centrolepidaceae	P
<i>Momipites punctatus</i> (Potonié) Nagy, 1969	Juglandaceae: Engelhardioideae: <i>Engelhardia</i> Leschenault & Blume, 1826, <i>Alfaroa</i> Standley, 1927, <i>Oreomunnea</i> Oersted, 1856	P2
<i>Momipites quietus</i> (Potonié) Nichols, 1973	Juglandaceae: Engelhardioideae: <i>Engelhardia</i> Leschenault & Blume, 1826, <i>Alfaroa</i> Standley, 1927, <i>Oreomunnea</i> Oersted, 1856	P
<i>Myricipites bituitus</i> (Potonié) Nagy, 1969	Myricaceae: <i>Myrica</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Myricipites megabituitus</i> (Pflug) Grabowska & Ważyńska in Stuchlik et al., 2009	Myricaceae: <i>Myrica</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Myricipites myricoides</i> (Kremp) Nagy, 1969	Myricaceae	P2/A1
<i>Myricipites</i> sp.	Myricaceae	P2/A
<i>Myrtaceoidites myrtiformis</i> Simoncsics, 1964	Myrtaceae	P/A1
<i>Nyssapollenites analepticus</i> (Potonié) Potonié ex Planderová, 1990	Nyssaceae: <i>Nyssa</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Nyssapollenites contortus</i> (Pflug & Thomson) Nagy, 1985	Nyssaceae: <i>Nyssa</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Nyssapollenites</i> sp.	Nyssaceae: <i>Nyssa</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Nyssoidites rodderensis</i> Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	Nyssaceae: <i>Nyssa</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Oleoidearumpollenites microreticulatus</i> (Pflug & Thomson) Ziemińska-Tworzydło in Ziemińska-Tworzydło et al., 1994	Oleaceae	P2/A1
<i>Oleoidearumpollenites reticulatus</i> Nagy, 1969	Oleaceae	P2/A1
<i>Oleoidearumpollenites</i> sp.	Oleaceae	P2/A1
<i>Oligopolis andreas</i> (Bruch) Durska in Stuchlik et al., 2014	unknown	unknown
<i>Parthenopollenites marcodurensis</i> (Pflug & Thomson) Traverse, 1994	Vitaceae	P/A1
<i>Periporopollenites orientalisformis</i> (Nagy) Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło in Stuchlik et al., 2009	Altingiaceae: <i>Liquidambar</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A1
<i>Periporopollenites stigmatosus</i> (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Altingiaceae: <i>Liquidambar</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A1
<i>Platanipollis ipelensis</i> (Pacltová) Grabowska in Ziemińska-Tworzydło et al., 1994	Platanaceae: <i>Platanus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P/A1
<i>Platycaryapollenites</i> sp.	Juglandaceae: <i>Platycarya</i> Siebold & Zuccarini, 1843	P2/A1
<i>Polyatriopollenites stellatus</i> (Potonié) Pflug, 1953	Juglandaceae: <i>Pterocarya</i> Kunth, 1824	A1
<i>Polyatriopollenites</i> sp.	Juglandaceae: <i>Pterocarya</i> Kunth, 1824	A1
<i>Quercoidites henricii</i> (Potonié) Potonié, Thomson & Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	Fagaceae: <i>Quercus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Quercoidites microhenricii</i> (Potonié) Potonié, Thomson & Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	Fagaceae: Quercoidae	P2/A1
<i>Quercopollenites</i> sp.	Fagaceae: <i>Quercus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A1
<i>Reevesiapollis microreticulatus</i> Krutzsch, 2004	Malvaceae: <i>Reevesia</i> Lindley, 1827	P
<i>Reevesiapollis</i> sp.	Malvaceae: <i>Reevesia</i> Lindley, 1827	P
<i>Restionioidites minimus</i> (Krutzsch) Kedves, 1974	Restionaceae, Centrolepidaceae, Flagellariaceae	P
<i>Rutacearumpollenites rutaceoides</i> Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło in Stuchlik et al., 2014	Rutaceae	P/A1
<i>Salixipollenites gracilis</i> Durska in Stuchlik et al., 2014	Salicaceae: <i>Salix</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A1
<i>Salixipollenites</i> sp.	Salicaceae: <i>Salix</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Sapotaceoideaepollenites manifestus</i> (Potonié) Potonié, Thomson & Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	Sapotaceae	P
<i>Sapotaceoideaepollenites obscurus</i> (Pflug & Thomson) Nagy, 1969	Sapotaceae	P
<i>Sapotaceoideaepollenites</i> sp.	Sapotaceae	P
<i>Sparganiaceaeepollenites</i> sp.	Sparganiaceae, Typhaceae	P/A
<i>Spinulaepollis arceuthobioides</i> Krutzsch, 1962	Santalaceae: <i>Arceuthobium</i> M. Bieb., 1819	P2/A1
<i>Subtriporopollenites</i> sp.	Juglandaceae?	P
<i>Symplocoipollenites calauensis</i> (Krutzsch) Grabowska in Stuchlik et al., 2014	Symplocaceae: <i>Symplocos</i> Jacquin, 1760	P
<i>Symplocoipollenites</i> sp.	Symplocaceae: <i>Symplocos</i> Jacquin, 1760	P
<i>Tetracolporopollenites sapotoides</i> Pflug & Thomson in Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Sapotaceae	P
<i>Tetracolporopollenites</i> sp.	Meliaceae?, Sapotaceae?	P
<i>Tricolporopollenites dolium</i> (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Fagaceae?	unknown
<i>Tricolporopollenites fallax</i> (Potonié) Krutzsch in Krutzsch et al., 1960	Fabaceae	P/A
<i>Tricolporopollenites liblarensis</i> (Thomson) Hochuli, 1978	Fabaceae	P/A
<i>Tricolporopollenites quisqualis</i> (Potonié) Krutzsch, 1954	Fabaceae	P/A
<i>Tricolporopollenites pseudocingulum</i> (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Fagaceae?, Styracaceae?	P/A1
<i>Tricolporopollenites staresdioensis</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová in Krutzsch, 1969	Hamamelidaceae	P2
<i>Tricolporopollenites villensis</i> (Thomson) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Fagaceae?	unknown

Table 1. — Continuation.

Fossil taxon	Botanical affinity	Element
<i>Tricolporopollenites</i> sp.	Fagaceae?	unknown
<i>Tripoporopollenites megagranifer</i> (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Betulaceae?, Ulmaceae?	P2/A1
<i>Tripoporopollenites undulatus</i> Pflug in Thomson & Pflug, 1953	unknown	P1
<i>Trivestibulopollenites betuloides</i> Pflug in Thomson & Pflug, 1953	Betulaceae: <i>Betula</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Ulmipollenites stillatus</i> Nagy, 1969	Ulmaceae: <i>Ulmus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A
<i>Ulmipollenites undulosus</i> Wolff, 1934	Ulmaceae: <i>Ulmus</i> Linnaeus, 1753	A2
<i>Vitispollenites tener</i> Thiele-Pfeiffer, 1980	Vitaceae: <i>Vitis</i> Linnaeus, 1753	P2/A1
<i>Zelkovaepollenites</i> sp.	Ulmaceae: <i>Zelkova</i> Spach, 1841	A1

ex Potonié emend. Krutzsch, 1961, *Platycaryapollenites* Nagy emend. Frederiksen & Christopher, 1978, and *Polyatriopollenites* Pflug, 1953), Fabaceae, and Ulmaceae (members of the fossil-genera *Celtipollenites* Nagy emend. Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 2009, *Ulmipollenites* Wolff, 1934, and *Zelkovaepollenites* Nagy, 1969). Pollen grains of *Aceripollenites* Nagy, 1969, *Arecipites* Wodehouse emend. Krutzsch, 1970, *Boehlensipollis bohli* Krutzsch, 1962, *Caprifoliipites* Wodehouse emend. Słodkowska, 2014, *Carpinipites carpinoides* (Pflug) Nagy, 1985, *Cercidiphylites minimireticulatus* (Trevisan) Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 1994, *Fraxinipollis* Słodkowska, 2014, *Intratripoporopollenites* Pflug & Thomson, 1953, *Milfordia* Erdtman, 1960, *Oleoidearumpollenites* Nagy, 1969, *Periporopollenites* Pflug & Thomson, 1953, *Reevesiapollis* Krutzsch, 1970, *Salixipollenites* Srivastava, 1967, *Sparganiaceapollenites* Thiergart emend. Krutzsch, 1970, *Subtripoporopollenites* Pflug & Thomson emend. Krutzsch, 1961, *Symplocoipollenites* Potonié ex Potonié, 1960, *Trivestibulopollenites betuloides* Pflug, 1953, and *Vitispollenites tener* Thiele-Pfeiffer, 1980, occur regularly. Pollen grains of *Cornaceapollis satzveyensis* (Pflug) Ziemińska-Tworzydło ex Jansonius *et al.*, 1998, *Faguspollenites* Raatz, 1937, and *Quercopollenites* Nagy, 1969 are more abundant in the upper part of the profile, while *Tricolporopollenites pseudocingulum* (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953 occurs only in the upper part. *Aglaoreidia cyclops* Erdtman, 1960, *Araliaceoipollenites* Potonié ex Potonié, 1960, *Cupanieidites eucalyptoides* Krutzsch, 1962, *Dicolpopollis* Pflanzl ex Potonié, 1966, *Dicolporopollis middendorfi* (Potonié) Krutzsch, 1961, *Edmundipollis* Konzalová, Słodkowska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 2014, *Meliaceoidites* Wang ex Jansonius & Hills, 1992, *Rutacearumpollenites rutaceoides* Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 2014, *Tripoporopollenites megagranifer* (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953, and several others are also recorded.

Spores of ferns, mainly from the fossil-genera *Baculatisporites* Pflug & Thomson, 1953, *Laevigatosporites* Ibrahim, 1933, *Leiotriletes* (Naumova) Potonié & Kremp, 1954, and *Neogenisporis* Krutzsch, 1962, plus fossil-species *Cicatricosisporites dorogensis* Potonié & Gelletich, 1933, were regularly encountered. Similarly, spores of Lycopodiaceae (*Camarozonosporites heskemensis* (Pflanzl) Krutzsch, 1959 and *Retritriletes* Pierce emend. Döring, Krutzsch, Mai & Schulz, 1963) and *Sphagnum*-related spores (members of the fossil-genera *Distancoaesporis* (Krutzsch) S.K.Srivastava, 1973 and *Stereisporites* Pflug, 1953) occur in most samples.

AQUATIC PALYNOMORPHS

Aquatic palynomorphs are present in all samples. Twenty fossil-species of freshwater and brackish algae other than dinoflagellate cysts were identified (Table 2). Colonies of *Botryococcus* Kützing, 1849 are present in most samples, but their abundance exceeds 1% only in the upper part of the profile. Single specimens of zygospores from Zygnemataceae (mainly members of the fossil-genus *Ovoidites* Potonié emend. Krutzsch, 1959), as well as prasinophycean algae (*Cymatiosphaera eupeplos* (Valesi) Deflandre, 1954), *Sigmopollis pseudosetarius* (Weyland & Pflug) Krutzsch & Pačtová, 1990, and acritarchs, occur. Several cenobia of *Pediastrum* Meyen, 1829 were encountered in the upper part of the profile.

Among the aquatic palynomorphs, dinoflagellate cysts dominate, the majority of which are thought to be of marine origin. The preliminary study of eleven samples (see chapter Material and methods) shows that they are present throughout the entire succession studied. Their high frequencies, the general homogeneity of the assemblages, and a very good state of preservation indicate that most of them are *in situ*, and their motile stages inhabited the photic zone of the basin during the accumulation of the strata in question. All samples studied for dinoflagellate cysts yielded gonyaulacacean-dominated assemblages composed mainly of representatives of *Glaphyrocysta* Stover & Evitt, 1978 and *Homotryblum* Davey & Williams, 1966, to a lesser extent of *Enneadocysta* Stover & Williams, 1995 and *Lingulodinium* D.Wall, 1967, which are less common, showing an increase in frequency only in some samples. Noteworthy is the rare occurrence of *Spiniferites* Mantell, 1850. Peridinoids are subordinate in most samples being almost exclusively represented by *Wetzeliella* Eisenack, 1938.

FUNGAL REMAINS

Fungal microremains are rare in all samples and do not exceed 1% of the palynological spectrum. They consist mainly of spores, including dictyosporites. In addition, some microsclerotia of terrestrial fungi were found in the samples from a depth of 86.9–87.3 m. These microsclerotia were intracellularly formed by fungi called dark septate endophytes (DSE) in the cortical cells of the plant roots. Microsclerotia consist of compact, darkly pigmented, thick-walled hyphae which previously filled usually the entire interior of the cortical cells tightly. They have various shapes depending on the shapes of the cells in which they were formed (Fig. 5N, O). Nowadays dark septate endophytes are darkly pigmented (melanised) fungi, mainly ascomycetes that colonise living plant

FIG. 4. — Pollen grains from Grabówka PIG-1: **A**, *Distachyapites* sp.; **B**, *Milfordia miocaenica* Grabowska & Stodkowska, 2009; **C**, **D**, *Restioniidites minimus* (Krutzsch) Kedves, 1974, same specimen, various foci; **E**, *Myricipites* sp.; **F**, *Aglaoreidia cyclops* Erdtman, 1960; **G**, *Ulmipollenites undulosus* Wolff, 1934; **H**, *Caryapollenites simplex* (Potonié) Raatz ex Potonié, 1960; **I**, *Momipites* cf. *punctatus* (Potonié) Nagy, 1969; **J**, *Platycaryapollenites* sp.; **K**, **L**, *Periporopollenites orientalisformis* (Nagy) Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 2009, same specimen, various foci; **M**, *Nyssapollenites* sp.; **N**, **O**, *Aceripollenites striatus* (Pflug) Thiele-Pfeiffer, 1980, same specimen, various foci; **P**, **Q**, *Ilexpollenites margaritatus* (Potonié) Thiergart, 1938, same specimen, various foci; **R**, *Tricolporopollenites staresedloensis* Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1969; **S**, *Faguspollenites* sp.; **T**, *Quercoidites microhenricii* (Potonié) Potonié, Thomson & Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960; **U**, *Tricolporopollenites pseudocingulum* (Potonié) Thomson & Pflug, 1953; **V**, *Tricolporopollenites villensis* (Thomson) Thomson & Pflug, 1953; **W**, *Fususpollenites fusus* (Potonié) Kedves, 1978; **X**, *Fususpollenites fusus* (Potonié) Kedves, 1978; **Y**, **Z**, *Fususpollenites fusus* (Potonié) Kedves, 1978, same specimen, various foci; **AA**, **BB**, *Caprifoliipites viburnoides* (Gruas-Cavagnetto) Kohlman-Adamska, 1994, same specimen, various foci; **CC-EE**, *Platanipollis ipelensis* (Pacltová) Grabowska, 1994, same specimen, various foci; **FF**, *Platanipollis ipelensis* (Pacltová) Grabowska, 1994. Scale bar: 10 µm.

TABLE 2. — Freshwater and brackish algae, recorded in samples from the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole. Botanical affinity and indication according to Kadłubowska (1984), Krutzsch & Pacltová (1990), Grabowska (1996a), van Geel & Grenfell (1996), and Worobiec (2010, 2011, 2014, and literature cited herein).

Taxon	Botanical affinity	Indication
<i>Acritarcha</i> indiff.	unknown	brackish waters?
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i> Kützing, 1849	Dictyosphaeriaceae: <i>Botryococcus braunii</i> Kützing, 1849	open water, fresh and brackish waters
<i>Closteritetrapidites</i> sp.	Closteriaceae: <i>Closterium</i> Nitzsch ex Ralfs, 1848	oligo- to eutrophic fresh waters
<i>Crassosphaera</i> sp.	Chlorophyta?, Prasinophyta?	brackish waters?
<i>Cymatiosphaera eupeplos</i> (Valesi) Deflandre, 1954	Prasinophyceae	brackish waters
<i>Diagonalites diagonalis</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Zygnemataceae: <i>Mougeotia laetevirens</i> (Braun) Wittrock, 1877 type	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Megatetrapidites megatetroides</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Zygnemataceae: <i>Mougeotia</i> Agardh, 1824	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Ovoidites elongatus</i> (Hunger) Krutzsch, 1959	Zygnemataceae: <i>Spirogyra</i> Link in Nees, 1820	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Ovoidites gracilis</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Zygnemataceae: <i>Spirogyra</i> Link in Nees, 1820	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Ovoidites grandis</i> (Pocock) Zippi, 1998	Zygnemataceae: <i>Spirogyra</i> Link in Nees, 1820	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Ovoidites ligneolus</i> (Potonié) Tomson & Pflug, 1953	Zygnemataceae: <i>Spirogyra</i> Link in Nees, 1820	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Ovoidites minoris</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Zygnemataceae: <i>Spirogyra</i> Link in Nees, 1820	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Pediastrum boryanum</i> (Turpin) Meneghini, 1840	Hydrodictyaceae: <i>Pediastrum boryanum</i> (Turpin) Meneghini, 1840	eutrophic fresh waters, open water surface
<i>Pediastrum simplex</i> Meyen, 1829	Hydrodictyaceae: <i>Pediastrum simplex</i> Meyen, 1829	eutrophic to mesotrophic fresh waters, open water surface
<i>Pediastrum</i> sp.	Hydrodictyaceae: <i>Pediastrum</i> Meyen, 1829	eutrophic to mesotrophic fresh waters, open water surface
<i>Planctonites stellarius</i> (Potonié) Krutzsch in Krutzsch <i>et al.</i> , 1960	Zygnematales: desmids	fresh and probably brackish waters
<i>Sigmpollis laevigatoides</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Chlorophyta?, other algae?	eutrophic to mesotrophic open fresh waters
<i>Sigmpollis pseudosetarius</i> (Weyland & Pflug) Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Chlorophyta?, other algae?	eutrophic to mesotrophic open fresh waters
<i>Stigmozygodites</i> sp.	Zygnemataceae: <i>Zygnema</i> Agardh, 1824	shallow, meso- to eutrophic, open fresh waters
<i>Tetrapidites foveolatooides</i> Krutzsch & Pacltová, 1990	Zygnemataceae: <i>Mougeotia</i> Agardh, 1824	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins
<i>Tetrapidites</i> sp.	Zygnemataceae: <i>Mougeotia</i> Agardh, 1824	shallow, stagnant, oxygen-rich fresh waters, lake margins

roots by forming both superficial and intraradical hyphae (Ruotsalainen *et al.* 2022). The ability to form intracellular microsclerotia is a unique feature of DSE among fungal plant root endophytes (Kariman *et al.* 2018: table 1). Dark septate endophytes colonize the roots of almost 600 modern plant species within 144 families (Jumpponen & Trappe 1998) in all major biomes of the world (Ruotsalainen *et al.* 2022). Similarly to mycorrhizal fungi, dark septate endophytes form close associations with plants both negative (parasitic) and symbiotic ones (Jumpponen 2001). The taxonomy of these fungi is rather complicated due to the lack of their sporulation and their morphological variability (Sieber 2002).

INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

AGE OF THE PALYNOFLORA

The composition of the palynological assemblage from the Grabówka PIG-1 clearly indicates its early Oligocene age. The stratigraphically most important pollen fossil-species

are *Boeblensipollis hobli* and *Cupanieidites eucalyptoides*. The ranges of these taxa are confined to the Rupelian-early Chattian (Grabowska 1996b) and they occur (usually in small numbers) in almost all Rupelian palynofloras from Poland. *Cicatricosisporites dorogensis* and *Aglaoreidia cyclops* are also stratigraphically important as their ranges end in the lower Oligocene (Grabowska 1974, 1996b; Krutzsch *et al.* 1992). The Rupelian spore-pollen spectra from various localities of the Polish Lowlands are taxonomically uniform. Gymnosperms are usually most abundant and, depending on whether the spectra come from brackish/marine or freshwater sediments, they are dominated by Pinaceae (*Pinuspollenites*) or Cupressaceae (*Inaperturopollenites* and *Sequoiapollenites*) pollen, respectively. Small tricolporate pollen grains from Fagaceae (mainly *Fususpollenites fusus*, but also *Cupuliferoipollenites pusillus* and *Quercoidites microhenricii*) almost always dominate among angiosperms. Palm and *Ephedra* pollen is more common in terrestrial sediments (Grabowska 1996b). For example, the Grabówka palynoflora studied here is very similar to spore-pollen assemblages from the 5th Lignite Seam of

FIG. 5. — Pollen grains and fungi from Grabówka PIG-1: **A, B**, *Myrtaceidites myrtiformis* (Kremp) Nagy, 1969, same specimen, various foci; **C**, *Symplocopollenites calauensis* (Krutzsch) Grabowska, 2014; **D**, *Intratriporopollenites insculptus* Mai, 1961; **E**, *Tetracolporopollenites sapotoides* Pflug & Thomson, 1953; **F**, *Ericipites triangulus* Grabowska, 2014; **G**, *Boehlensipollis hohli* Krutzsch, 1962; **H**, *Boehlensipollis hohli* Krutzsch, 1962; **I**, *Boehlensipollis hohli* Krutzsch, 1962; **J-M**, *Arecipites pseudoconvexus* Krutzsch, 1970, same specimen, various foci; **N**, microsclerotium of DSE fungus; **O**, microsclerotium of DSE fungus; **P, Q**, dictyosporous fungus, same specimen, various foci. Scale bar: 10 μ m.

the Warszyce 19 borehole, central Poland (Grabowska 1969 *vide in* Kasiński & Słodkowska 2016) as well as it resembles very closely palynofloras from the lower Oligocene of the Pomeranian Lakeland (Słodkowska 2004a), Warmia and Mazury (Słodkowska 2009), and the Middle Vistula Valley (Słodkowska 2004b). The most important taxa in those palynofloras were: *Fususpollenites fusus*, *Quercoidites microhenricii*, *Cupuliferoipollenites pusillus*, *Inaperturopollenites* sp. (Cupressaceae), *Sequoiapollenites*, *Cyrillaceapollenites*, *Myricipites*, *Tricolporopollenites liblarensis*, *T. quisqualis*, *Pinuspollenites*, *Tricolporopollenites dolium*, *T. villensis*, *Platanipollis ipelensis*, *Momipites*, *Boehlensipollis hohli*, *Dicolporopollenites*

middendorfi, *Milfordia incerta*, *Triporopollenites megagrifer*, *Camarozonosporites heskemensis*, *Cicatricosisporites dorogensis*, and *Cupanieidites eucalyptoides*.

Most of the angiosperm taxa mentioned above also occur in the lower Oligocene palynofloras from southern Poland (upland area separating the Polish Lowlands in the north and Carpathians in the south), but in those palynological assemblages, the lack of marine palynomorphs and the low frequency of bisaccate pollen grains are characteristic. Those strata, with lignites correlated with the 5th lignite seam group, were deposited in isolated basins and the phytogenic terrestrial accumulation took place under continental, freshwater

conditions, most likely in a swampy-lacustrine environment, as indicated by the presence of *Botryococcus* in spectra from the Łukowa-4 borehole, SE Poland (Gedl *et al.* 2016), or in karst sinkholes in south-western Poland (Worobiec & Szulc 2020).

Such a homogeneous composition of spore-pollen spectra makes the deposits of the lower Oligocene (including the 5th group of lignite seams) a good correlation horizon throughout the Polish Lowlands. Moreover, the 5th lignite seam is correlated with the 5th Lusatian (Lausitz) Lignite Seam in the eastern territory of Germany (Widera 2016). For example, the Calau Beds in Brandenburg, Germany, which represent estuarine to continental, lignite-bearing deposits (the 5th Lusatian Lignite Seam), yielded e.g. stratigraphically significant elements like: *Aglaoreidia cyclops*, *Boehlensipollis hobli*, *Dicolpopollis middendorfi*, *Camarozonosporites heskemensis*, *Cicatricosisporites paradorogensis*, *Plicapollis pseudoexcelsus* group, *Pentapollenites* sp., *Porocolpopollenites calauensis* as well as the group of smooth pollen grains of palms (Kruttsch *et al.* 1992; Mai 1998, and the literature cited therein).

Diversified early Oligocene plant assemblages known from marine deposits occur in the Upper Rhine Graben (Bodenheim Formation) and in the Paratethys region (Kvaček 2004; Hably & Erdei 2015; Kovar-Eder 2016). In contrast, the early Oligocene floras from the Czech Republic (northern Bohemia) and adjacent parts of Germany (mainly Saxony) originate mainly from lacustrine deposits in the adjacent volcanic hinterland (volcanic floras *sensu* Kvaček & Walther 2001 and Walther & Kvaček 2007) or were deposited in coastal lowlands (Leipzig Embayment; Mai & Walther 1978). Despite the differences in the composition of individual spore-pollen assemblages, *Boehlensipollis hoblii* is among the early Oligocene index sporomorphs found in those floras (Mai & Walther 1978; Konzalová 1981; Pross *et al.* 2001; Walther & Kvaček 2007).

SEDIMENTARY SETTING

The presence of numerous dinoflagellate cysts throughout the whole Grabówka PIG-1 succession clearly indicates that these deposits accumulated in the marine environment. The composition of their assemblages shows a proximal, littoral setting as most species present, such as *Glaphyrocyta*, *Homotryblium*, *Membranophoridium*, *Lingulodinium*, are commonly found in rocks deposited in proximal marine environments (e.g. Köthe 1991; Brinkhuis 1994). Simultaneously, dinoflagellate cyst assemblages from Grabówka PIG-1 lack offshore species such as *Impagidinium* (e.g. Harland 1983; Brinkhuis 1994; Zonneveld *et al.* 2013). The near-shore environment can also be inferred from the presence of fungal microsclerotia of terrestrial DSE. Fungal remains represent palynological traces of terrestrial fluxes into the marine settings washed away from the adjacent lands (de Vernal 2009) and tend to accumulate in most proximal sites, decreasing basinward (Farr 1989; van Waveren 1989; Oboh 1992; Tyson 1995). The presence of algae, such as *Botryococcus*, Zygnemataceae, *Pediastrum*, and *Sigmopollis*, which are restricted to freshwater environments (Kadłubowska 1984; Guy-Ohlson 1992; Batten & Grenfell 1996; van Geel & Grenfell 1996; Zippi 1998), also suggests proximity to land.

All the sporomorphs found must have been transported from their vegetation areas into the marine basin where they were deposited. Fortunately, several studies show that the composition of the palynological assemblages from neritic marine sediments correlates well with the main types of contemporary terrestrial plant communities. Moreover, the percentage of pollen in marine sediments generally reflects the vegetation of the surrounding area and can roughly be used for palaeoclimatic considerations (e.g. Mudie 1982; Heusser 1983; Hooghiemstra & Agwu 1986; Van der Kaars 2001; Luo *et al.* 2014; Prader *et al.* 2017). Due to the fact that terrestrial elements are transported over different distances by water and air, these marine spore-pollen spectra may be used for the reconstruction of past environments only with great caution. For example, in marine sediments, bisaccate pollen (mainly *Pinus*) is usually over-represented, while other elements (for example pollen of insect-pollinated plants) are reduced (the so-called Neves Effect; e.g. Traverse 2007). Nevertheless, the large number of samples we analysed also allowed us to encounter some of these rarer pollen grains and spores (see chapters above).

TERRESTRIAL VEGETATION

The results of the palynological analysis indicate the presence of lush vegetation on the nearby land. Mixed mesophytic forests that grew there were composed of members of the Fagaceae family (*Colombobalanus/Trigonobalanus*, Castaneoideae, evergreen *Quercus* and others), *Platanus*, Engelhardioideae, *Platyacarya* as well as *Carpinus*, *Cercidiphyllum*, *Reevesia*, *Symplocos*, members of the Adoxaceae, Araliaceae, Arecaceae, Cornaceae, Fabaceae, Hamamelidaceae, Mastixiaceae, Meliaceae, Oleaceae and Sapotaceae families, conifers, and others. Many of them are thermophilous taxa. *Acer*, *Alnus*, *Carya*, *Celtis*, *Fraxinus*, *Liquidambar*, *Nyssa*, *Pterocarya*, *Salix*, *Ulmus*, and Vitaceae were most likely elements of wetland (swamp or riparian) forests. Shrubs from the Clethraceae and/or Cyrillaceae, Ericaceae and Myricaceae families, *Ilex* and some palms were probably components of shrub bog communities. Some pollen grains of conifers, e.g. *Pinus* and *Sciadopitys* could also have grown in wet places and/or in the margins of peat-bogs (Mosbrugger *et al.* 1994; Figueiral *et al.* 1999; Richardson 2003; Kus *et al.* 2020). Among the Cupressaceae are members of the Taxodioideae and Sequoioideae subfamilies, producing pollen of various morphologies (Fig. 3G-J), including the group of taxa with long papillae (Bouchal & Denk 2020). *Cryptomeria*, *Glyptostrobus*, *Metasequoia*, *Sequoia*, *Sequoiadendron*, and *Taxodium* were most likely components of different plant communities. For example, *Glyptostrobus* and *Taxodium*, together with *Nyssa*, could have grown in swamp forests in permanently flooded areas. The *Taxodium-Nyssa* swamp forests, often with *Glyptostrobus* and *Alnus*, were widespread in Europe during the Oligocene to Pliocene period as a type of Neogene peat bog vegetation (Mai 1981, 1995). *Sequoia* presumably has grown in wet places as well (Schneider 1992; Holdgate *et al.* 2016; Worobiec *et al.* 2021); some authors consider it as a riparian element (Kovar-Eder *et al.* 2001). Pollen of *Milfordia* and *Aglaoreidia cyclops* can probably be

TABLE 3. — Fossil taxa used for the estimation of the mean annual temperature (MAT) based on the Coexistence Approach (CA) method (Utescher *et al.* 2014). The nearest living relatives and their MAT ranges follow The Palaeoflora Database (Utescher & Mosbrugger 2015; Utescher *et al.* 2024).

Fossil taxa	Nearest living relatives	MAT range [°C]
<i>Aceripollenites</i> spp.	<i>Acer</i>	−1.1–24.0
<i>Alnipollenites</i> spp.	<i>Alnus</i>	−13.3–27.4
<i>Carpinipites carpinooides</i> (Pflug) Nagy, 1985	<i>Carpinus</i>	0.0–25.8
<i>Caryapollenites</i> spp.	<i>Carya</i>	4.4–26.6
<i>Celtipollenites</i> sp.	<i>Celtis</i>	2.5–25.8
<i>Cercidiphyllites minimireticulatus</i> (Trevisan) Ziemińska-Tworzydło, 1994	<i>Cercidiphyllum</i>	2.2–17.8
<i>Cornaceapollis satzveyensis</i> (Pflug) Ziemińska-Tworzydło ex Jansonius <i>et al.</i> , 1998	<i>Mastixia</i>	15.7–27.8
<i>Cornaceapollis</i> sp.	<i>Cornus</i>	−12–23.1
<i>Corylopsispollenites microreticulatus</i> E.Worobiec, 2014	<i>Corylopsis</i>	9.1–25.5
<i>Faguspollenites</i> spp.	<i>Fagus</i>	4.4–23.1
<i>Fraxinipollis</i> spp.	<i>Fraxinus</i>	0.0–24.0
<i>Fususpollenites fusus</i> (Potonié) Kedves, 1978	<i>Trigonobalanus</i> s.l. (incl. <i>Colombobalanus</i>)	17.2–27.7
<i>Ilexpollenites</i> spp.	<i>Ilex</i>	−0.4–27.7
<i>Juglanspollenites</i> sp.	<i>Juglans</i>	0.0–27.5
<i>Magnoliaepollenites</i> sp.	<i>Magnolia</i>	4.1–27.0
<i>Myricipites</i> spp.	<i>Myrica</i>	−8.9–28.1
<i>Nyssapollenites</i> spp.	<i>Nyssa</i>	4.4–23.9
<i>Nyssoidites rodderensis</i> Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	<i>Nyssa</i>	4.4–23.9
<i>Periporopollenites</i> spp.	<i>Liquidambar</i>	11.5–25.5
<i>Platanipollis ipelensis</i> (Pacltová) Grabowska, 1994	<i>Platanus</i>	6.6–27.4
<i>Platycaryapollenites</i> sp.	<i>Platycarya</i>	6.9–23.1
<i>Polyatriopollenites</i> spp.	<i>Pterocarya</i>	3.9–24.2
<i>Quercoidites henricii</i> (Potonié) Potonié, Thomson & Thiergart ex Potonié, 1960	<i>Quercus</i> (evergreen)	8.7–22.1
<i>Quercopollenites</i> spp.	<i>Quercus</i> (deciduous)	−1.4–27.0
<i>Reevesiapollis</i> spp.	<i>Reevesia</i>	13.5–25.5
<i>Salixipollenites</i> sp.	<i>Salix</i>	−17.0–27.7
<i>Spinulaepollis arceuthobioides</i> Krutzsch, 1962	<i>Arceuthobium</i>	−5.5–27.7
<i>Symplocoipollenites</i> spp.	<i>Symplocos</i>	4.5–27.7
<i>Trivestibulopollenites betuloides</i> Pflug, 1953	<i>Betula</i>	−15.0–25.8
<i>Ulmipollenites</i> spp.	<i>Ulmus</i>	−4.9–26.6
<i>Vitispollenites tener</i> Thiele-Pfeiffer, 1980	<i>Vitis</i>	0.0–27.4
<i>Zelkovaepollenites</i> sp.	<i>Zelkova</i>	6.2–21.9

considered as representatives of the freshwater/marsh vegetation (e.g. Akkiraz *et al.* 2006). Similarly, Sparganiaceae and/or Typhaceae, and Cyperaceae grew in wet places. Among the ferns and lycopods several thermophilous taxa, including members of the Lygodiaceae, Schizaeaceae, Cyatheaceae and/or Gleicheniaceae families, were present.

Fossil pollen of *Ephedra* is known to be an indicator of a dry palaeoclimate (Bolinder *et al.* 2016) because modern members of this genus are xeromorphic. However, *Ephedra* species today also grow under more humid climate conditions on dry soils such as seashores with direct sun exposure. Moreover, according to Frink & Szabó (2009), the current relict sites of *Ephedra distachya* in Romania mark the seashore level of the Pannonian Sea before its regression at the end of the Neogene.

PALAEOCLIMATE

Pollen and spore taxa of thermophilic plants, including “warm-temperate” and “palaeotropical/warm-temperate” (Table 1), play a significant role or even dominate in the palynoflora studied. The presence of plant genera, growing now under tropical and subtropical climatic conditions, is clearly visible throughout the palynological diagram. Among them are members of the pantropical families Meliaceae and Sapotaceae as well as the subtropical-tropical families Arecaceae, Schizaeaceae, Cyatheaceae and/or Gleicheniaceae. This observation

indicates that the climate during the sedimentation of the deposits studied was very warm (subtropical) and humid. It cannot be ruled out that fluctuations in the frequency of individual plant taxa are caused by climatic fluctuations, but the changes in the abundance of dinoflagellate cysts show that these are mainly caused by changes in the sea level and the distance of the sedimentation site from land.

The narrowest range of mean annual temperature (MAT) that can be estimated for the Grabówka PIG-1 palynoflora is 17.2–17.8°C (Table 3); with the bordering taxa *Fususpollenites fusus*, related to the genus *Trigonobalanus* s.l. (incl. *Colombobalanus*) (17.2–27.7°C), and *Cercidiphyllites minimireticulatus*, related to the *Cercidiphyllum* genus (2.2–17.8°C). It should be mentioned that *Cercidiphyllites minimireticulatus* was found in eight samples from different parts of the profile (Fig. 6). *Fususpollenites fusus* is present in all samples, but its botanical affinity is not entirely certain (Kohlman-Adamska & Ziemińska-Tworzydło 2001; Stuchlik *et al.* 2014). *Quercoidites microhenricii* and *Q. henricii*, common in all studied samples, could indicate that the MAT ranged up to 22.1°C (8.7–22.1°C); they are related to evergreen oaks from several different sections of the *Quercus* genus (MAT range and botanical affinity based on Utescher & Mosbrugger 2015). Therefore, the wider, but probably less error-prone, MAT range for the studied palynoflora is 15.7–23.1°C; with the bordering taxa *Cornaceapollis satzveyensis*, related to the

Mastixia genus (15.7–27.8°C), and *Platycaryapollenites* sp., related to the *Platycarya* genus (6.9–23.1°C) or *Faguspollenites* sp., related to the *Fagus* genus (4.4–23.1°C).

Previous studies indicate a typical humid subtropical climate with distinct seasonality in central Europe during the Oligocene (Zachos *et al.* 2001, 2008; Mosbrugger *et al.* 2005; Li *et al.* 2018; Westerhold *et al.* 2020). Indeed, not all paratropical taxa found in the Eocene Climatic Optimum disappeared immediately, but some persisted into the early Oligocene (Collinson & Hooker 2003). Moreover, the timing and scale of this floral transition were not uniform in various regions of central and southeastern Europe (Kvaček & Walther 2001; Utescher *et al.* 2021). For example, in the Calau flora the following families were represented: Adiantaceae (C.Presl) R.M.Tryon, Altingiaceae Horaninow, Arecaceae Martius ex Dumortier, Betulaceae Gray, Cornaceae Berchtold & J.Presl, Dennstaedtiaceae Lotsy, Elaeagnaceae Jussieu, Ephedraceae Dumortier, Eucommiaceae Engler, Fagaceae Dumortier, Gleicheniaceae C.Presl, Juglandaceae Perleb, Loranthaceae s.l., Lycopodiaceae P.Beauvois, Mastixiaceae Calestani, Myricaceae Kunth, Nepenthaceae Dumortier, Onagraceae Jussieu, Osmundaceae Martinov, Pinaceae F.Rudolphi, Polypodiaceae J.Presl & C.Presl, Restionaceae R.Brown, Sapotaceae Jussieu, Schizaeaceae Kaulfman, Sciadopityaceae Luersson, Sparganiaceae Hanin, Sterculioideae Beilschmied, Symplocaceae Desfontaines, Taxodiaceae Saporta = Cupressaceae Bartlink, Tilioidae Arnott, and Ulmaceae Mirbel. Those included plants there were many taxa with high thermal requirements, but also plants whose living relatives grow in temperate climates. The composition of the fossil flora from Calau suggests a mixed mesophytic forest vegetation growing under humid temperate (subtropical) climatic conditions (Mai 1998). Similarly, the lignites of the 5th group of seams in the Polish Lowlands originated within isolated wetland basins, surrounded by very lush and mostly mesophilous vegetation with numerous highly thermophilous plants (Grabowska 1996b; Słodkowska 2004a, 2004b). The climate at that time was warm and humid, with the MAT in the range of 17.2–23.9°C and mean annual precipitation between 1 217 and 1 520 mm, when *Trigonobalanus* was used in the CA analysis (Kasiński & Słodkowska 2016). The palaeoclimate corresponded to a subtropical climate (Cfa type) in the sub-division of Köppen (Kottek *et al.* 2006), characterised by hot, usually humid, summers and mild winters (Kasiński & Słodkowska 2016). Palaeoclimatic conditions during the sedimentation of the middle Rupel Clay in the Mainz Basin, estimated based on the CA, also revealed a warm and humid palaeoclimate. MAT ranged from 16 to 18°C, the mean coldest month temperature 6–10°C, the mean warmest month temperature 25–28°C, and the mean annual precipitation 1 000–1 300 mm (Pross *et al.* 1998, 2001; Kvaček 2004). Other examples are from sites in Saxony, Germany, where MAT was estimated for the lowermost Oligocene Beucha site at 15.6–16.1°C, upper lower Oligocene Haselbach site at 15.7–18.3°C, and lower Oligocene Regis III site at 16.5–23.9°C; with hot summers and mild winters, and mean annual precipitation in the range of 897–1 281 mm (Roth-Nebelsick *et al.* 2004).

SEA WATER TEMPERATURE

Aquatic palynomorphs from the Grabówka PIG-1 succession do not allow a direct reconstruction of seawater temperature; none of the species found has precisely known water temperature preferences that could suggest their value. The only suggestions excluding cold-water conditions can be based on the absence of high-latitude dinoflagellate cyst species, like *Svalbardella cooksoniae* or *Impagidinium velorum*, which are considered indicators of cold-water northward migrations during the early Oligocene (e.g. Gedl 2004; Van Simaey *et al.* 2005; Śliwińska & Heilmann-Clausen 2011). This somehow contrasts with the palaeotemperature data obtained for the early Oligocene sea water from the north-western Polish Lowlands based on foraminifera analysis. Odrzywolska-Bieńkowska *et al.* (1978) suggested cool water conditions, though without precise values. That interpretation was based on foraminifera associations (mainly benthic) from marine strata occurring in the north-western Polish Lowlands. The bottom waters (and hence the benthic foraminifera) in this area were likely intensively influenced by the cold and dense waters exchanged from the North Sea basin, where isotopic evidence suggests a significant temperature drop (e.g. Buchardt 1978). These changes were not necessarily associated with climatic changes and the near-shore embayment, where the investigated Czempień Formation was probably accumulated, may lie beyond the reach of cold bottom waters of the main part of the basin.

However, the absence of cold-water dinoflagellate cysts does not necessarily solve the problem of water temperature conditions. Firstly, the investigated Czempień Formation is a near-shore facies without offshore species such as *Impagidinium velorum*. Although palaeoenvironmental preferences of *Svalbardella cooksoniae* are not precisely known (except for its cold-water preferences), Śliwińska & Head (2020) suggested that its sister species *Svalbardella kareniae* favoured offshore waters. Moreover, the lack of peridinioid *S. cooksoniae* in the present material can be explained by generally hostile conditions for peridinioids, which are scarce (mainly Wetzeliellaceae). Secondly, the strata in question are presumably slightly younger than the earliest Oligocene cooling event responsible for the appearance of cool-water species as far south as the Carpathian basins (see e.g. Gedl 2004). The studied strata are also slightly older than another cooling event that, according to Van Simaey *et al.* (2005), occurred close to or at the boundary between the Rupelian and the Chattian and was also manifested by the appearance of *Svalbardella* at lower latitudes.

CONCLUSIONS

The samples from the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole yielded rich palynological material consisting of terrestrial and marine palynomorphs. The composition of the palynoflora, including such stratigraphically important fossil-species as *Boehlensipollis hobli*, *Cupanieidites eucalyptoides*, *Cicatricosisporites dorogensis*, and *Aglaoreidia cyclops*, clearly indicates its early Oligocene age.

Fig. 6. — Simplified percentage diagram of pollen and spores of plants, and non-pollen palynomorphs from the Grabówka PIG-1 borehole. **Black bars** show percentages (%), **white bars** show percentages $\times 10$ (‰).

The composition of the spore-pollen assemblage corresponds to the 5th Czempin lignite seam group. The presence of dinoflagellate cysts throughout the succession studied clearly indicates that it was deposited under marine conditions. The whole sequence was deposited in a near-shore environment of the epicontinental sea connected with the North Sea. The proximity to land is indicated by large amounts of terrestrial plant remains and freshwater algae. The presence of fungal microsclerotia (dark septate endophytes) in the lower part of the profile may also suggest proximity to the coastline.

The results of the spore-pollen analysis indicate the presence of lush vegetation with numerous thermophilous elements (including members of the pantropical families Meliaceae and Sapotaceae as well as the subtropical-tropical families Arecaceae, Schizaeaceae, Cyatheaceae and/or Gleicheniaceae, plus many “warm-temperate” taxa) in the adjacent land area. Mixed mesophytic forests were composed mainly of members of the Fagaceae and Juglandaceae families as well as *Platanus*, *Carpinus*, *Cercidiphyllum*, *Reevesia*, *Symplocos*, members of the Adoxaceae, Araliaceae, Arecaceae, Cornaceae, Fabaceae, Hamamelidaceae, Mastixiaceae, Meliaceae, Oleaceae and Sapotaceae families. There were also wetland (swamp or riparian) forests, shrub bogs, and freshwater/marsh vegetation. *Ephedra* grew on seashores. The climate during the sedimentation of the deposits was subtropical and humid, with the estimated MAT range of 15.7–23.1°C.

Acknowledgements

We thank Angela A. Bruch and Mehmet Serkan Akkiraz for their valuable comments on this article. The associated editor Anaïs Boura, the editor-in-chief Michel Laurin, and the desk editor Audrina Neveu are also thanked. This study contributes to NECLIME – an open international network of scientists working on the Cenozoic climate evolution and related changes in continental ecosystems.

Funding

This work was supported by the W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, through its statutory funds to Elżbieta and Grzegorz Worobiec. The drilling was performed by the Polish Geological Institute-National Research Institute as part of the project: “Integrated program of shallow research drilling to solve important problems of the geological structure of Poland” no. 21.9100.0501.00.0, financed by the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management.

REFERENCES

AKKIRAZ M. S., AKGÜN F., ÖRCEN S., BRUCH A. A. & MOSBRUGGER V. 2006. — Stratigraphic and palaeoenvironmental significance of Bartonian–Priabonian (middle–late Eocene) microfossils from the Bascemes Formation, Denizli Province, Western Anatolia. *Turkish Journal of Earth Sciences* 15 (2): 155–180. <https://journals.tubitak.gov.tr/earth/vol15/iss2/3>

BATTEN D. J. & GRENFELL H. R. 1996. — *Botryococcus*, in JANSONIUS J. & MCGREGOR D. C. (eds), *Palynology: Principles and Applications*. American Association of Stratigraphic Palynologists Foundation. Vol. 1. Dallas, Texas: 205–214.

BOLINDER K., NORBÄCK IVARSSON L., HUMPHREYS A. M., ICKERT-BOND S. M., HAN F., HOORN C. & RYDIN C. 2016. — Pollen morphology of *Ephedra* (Gnetales) and its evolutionary implications. *Grana* 55 (1): 24–51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00173134.2015.1066424>

BOUCHAL J. M. & DENK T. 2020. — Low taxonomic resolution of papillate Cupressaceae pollen (former Taxodiaceae) impairs their applicability for palaeo-habitat reconstruction. *Grana* 59 (1): 71–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00173134.2019.1701704>

BRINKHUIS H. 1994. — Late Eocene to Early Oligocene dinoflagellate cysts from the Priabonian type-area (northeast Italy); biostratigraphy and palaeoenvironmental interpretation. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 107 (1–2): 121–163. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182\(94\)90168-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182(94)90168-6)

BUCHARDT B. 1978. — Oxygen isotope palaeotemperatures from the Tertiary period in the North Sea area. *Nature* 275: 121–123. <https://doi.org/10.1038/275121a0>

COLLINSON M. E. & HOOKER J. J. 2003. — Paleogene vegetation of Eurasia: framework for mammalian faunas. *Deinsea* 10: 41–83.

COXALL H. K. & PEARSON P. N. 2007. — The Eocene–Oligocene transition, in WILLIAMS M. (ed.), *Deep-time perspectives on climate change: marrying the signal from computer models and biological proxies*. The Micropalaeontological Society, Special Publications, Geological Society of London: 351–387.

COXALL H. K. & WILSON P. A. 2011. — Early Oligocene glaciation and productivity in the eastern equatorial Pacific: insights into global carbon cycling. *Paleoceanography* 26: PA2221. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010PA002021>

DE VERNAL A. 2009. — Marine palynology and its use for studying nearshore environments, in: Deep-sea to coastal zones: methods and techniques for studying paleoenvironments. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 5: 012002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1307/5/1/012002>

FARR K. 1989. — Palynomorph and palynodebris distributions in modern British and Irish estuarine sediments, in BATTEN D. J. & KEEN M. C. (eds), *Northwest European Micropalaeontology and Palynology*. British Micropalaeontological Society Series, Ellis Horwood, Chichester: 265–85.

FIGUEIRAL I., MOSBRUGGER V., ROWE N. P., ASHRAF A. R., UTESCHER T. & JONES T. P. 1999. — The Miocene peat-forming vegetation of northwestern Germany: an analysis of wood remains and comparison with previous palynological interpretations. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 104 (3–4): 239–266. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-6667\(98\)00059-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-6667(98)00059-1)

FRINK J. P. & SZABÓ A. 2009. — Distribution of *Ephedra distachya* L. subsp. *distachya* in Transylvania (Romania) with special regards to new occurrences. *Kanitzia* 16: 119–132.

GEDL P. 2004. — Dinoflagellate cyst record of the Eocene–Oligocene boundary succession in flysch deposits at Leluchów, Carpathian Mountains, Poland, in BEAUDOIN A. B. & HEAD M. J. (eds), *The Palynology and Micropalaeontology of Boundaries*. Geological Society, London, Special Publications 230: 309–324. <https://doi.org/10.1144/GSL.SP.2004.230.01.16>

GEDL P., WOROBIEC E. & SŁODKOWSKA B. 2016. — Palynology of Lower Oligocene brown coal and lowermost Middle Miocene sand deposits from the Łukowa-4 borehole (Carpathian Foredeep, SE Poland) – implications for palaeogeographical reconstructions. *Geological Quarterly* 60: 943–958. <https://doi.org/10.7306/gq.1305>

GRABOWSKA I. 1969. — *Rewizja pozycji stratygraficznej osadów węglowych z rejonu Rogóżna na podstawie analizy sporowo-pyłkowej*. Unpublished. National Geological Archive, no. 4129/812, Warszawa.

- GRABOWSKA I. 1974. — Stratigraphy of Palaeogene Sediments in the Polish Lowlands in the Light of Research on Microflora. *Biuletyn Instytutu Geologicznego* 281 (7): 67-90 (in Polish with English summary).
- GRABOWSKA I. 1996a. — Chlorophyta, in MALINOWSKA L. & PIWOCKI M. (eds), *Budowa geologiczna Polski 3. Atlas skamieniałości przewodnich i charakterystycznych 3a. Kenozoik, trzeciorzęd, paleogen*. Polska Agencja Ekologiczna, Warszawa: 387-391.
- GRABOWSKA I. 1996b. — Flora sporowo-pyłkowa, in MALINOWSKA L. & PIWOCKI M. (eds), *Budowa geologiczna Polski 3. Atlas skamieniałości przewodnich i charakterystycznych 3a. Kenozoik, trzeciorzęd, paleogen*. Polska Agencja Ekologiczna, Warszawa: 395-431.
- GRABOWSKA I. & PIWOCKI M. 1975. — The age and origin of the Toruń clays from the vicinity of Toruń defined on the basis of palynological and lithological observations. *Biuletyn Instytutu Geologicznego* 284: 41-70.
- GRABOWSKA I. & SŁODKOWSKA B. 1993. — *Katalog profili osadów trzeciorzędowych opracowanych palinologicznie*. PiG, Warszawa, 80 p.
- GUY-OHLSON D. 1992. — *Botryococcus* as an aid in the interpretation of palaeoenvironment and depositional processes. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 71 (1-4): 1-15. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-6667\(92\)90155-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-6667(92)90155-A)
- HABLY L. & ERDEI B. 2015. — The early Oligocene flora and palaeo-environment of the Tard Clay Formation – latest results. *Hantkeniana* 10: 113-124. <http://real.mtak.hu/id/eprint/94922>
- HARLAND R. 1983. — Distribution maps of recent dinoflagellate cysts in bottom sediments from the North Atlantic Ocean and adjacent seas. *Palaeontology* 26: 321-387.
- HEUSSER L. E. 1983. — Pollen distribution in the bottom sediments of the western North Atlantic Ocean. *Marine Micropaleontology* 8 (1): 77-88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-8398\(83\)90006-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-8398(83)90006-3)
- HOLDGATE G., WALLACE M., O'CONNOR M., KORASIDIS V. & LIEVEN U. 2016. — The origin of lithotype cycles in Oligo-Miocene brown coals from Australia and Germany. *International Journal of Coal Geology* 12: 327-347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coal.2016.05.010>
- HOOGHIEMSTRA H. & AGWU C. O. C. 1986. — Distribution of palynomorphs in marine sediments: a record for seasonal wind patterns over NW Africa and adjacent Atlantic. *Geologische Rundschau* 75: 81-95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01770180>
- HUTCHINSON D. K., COXALL H. K., LUNT, D. J., STEINTHORS-DOTTIR M., DE BOER A. M., BAATSEN M., VON DER HEYDT A., HUBER M., KENNEDY-ASSER A. T., KUNZMANN L., LADANT J.-B., LEAR C. H., MORAWECK K., PEARSON P. N., PIGA E., POUND M. J., SALZMANN U., SCHER H. D., SIJF W. P., ŚLIWIŃSKA K. K., WILSON P. A. & ZHAN Z. 2021. — The Eocene-Oligocene transition: a review of marine and terrestrial proxy data, models and model-data comparisons. *Climate of the Past* 17 (1): 269-315. <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-17-269-2021>
- JUMPPONEN A. 2001. — Dark septate endophytes – are they mycorrhizal? *Mycorrhiza* 11 (4): 207-211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s005720100112>
- JUMPPONEN A. R. I. & TRAPPE J. M. 1998. — Dark septate endophytes: a review of facultative biotrophic root-colonizing fungi. *The New Phytologist* 140 (2): 295-310. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1469-8137.1998.00265.x>
- KADLUBOWSKA J. Z. 1984. — *Süßwasserflora von Mitteleuropa. Band 16: Chlorophyta VIII-Conjugatophyceae I (Zygnemales)*. Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart, 532 p.
- KARIMAN K., BARKER S. J. & TIBBETT M. 2018. — Structural plasticity in root-fungal symbioses: diverse interactions lead to improved plant fitness. *PeerJ* 6: e6030. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6030>
- KASIŃSKI J. R. & SŁODKOWSKA B. 2016. — Factors controlling Cenozoic anthracogenesis in the Polish Lowlands. *Geological Quarterly* 60: 959-974. <https://doi.org/10.7306/gq.1321>
- KENNETT J. P. 1977. — Cenozoic evolution of Antarctic glaciation, the circum-Antarctic Ocean, and their impact on global paleoceanography. *Journal of geophysical research* 82 (27): 3843-3860. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC082i027p03843>
- KENNETT J. P. & SHACKLETON N. J. 1976. — Oxygen isotopic evidence for the development of the psychrosphere 38 Myr ago. *Nature* 260: 513-515. <https://doi.org/10.1038/260513a0>
- KOHLMAN-ADAMSKA A. & ZIEMBIŃSKA-TWORZYDŁO M. 2001. — Morphological variability and botanical affinity of *Fususpollenites* Kedves 1978 (LM and SEM investigations). *Acta Palaeobotanica* 41 (2): 147-159.
- KONZALOVÁ M. 1981. — *Boehleispollis* und andere Mikrofossilien des böhmischen Tertiärs (vulkanogene Schichtenfolge). *Sborník Geologických Věd, Paleontologie* 24: 135-162.
- KOTTEK M., GRIESER J., BECK C., RUDOLF B. & RUBEL F. 2006. — World Map of Köppen Geiger Climate Classification updated. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift* 15 (3): 259-263. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2006/0130>
- KOVAR-EDER J. 2016. — Early Oligocene plant diversity along the Upper Rhine Graben: the fossil flora of Rauenberg, Germany. *Acta Palaeobotanica* 56 (2): 329-440. <https://doi.org/10.1515/acpa-2016-0011>
- KOVAR-EDER J., KVAČEK Z. & MELLER B. 2001. — Comparing Early to Middle Miocene floras and probable vegetation types of Oberdorf N Voitsberg (Austria), Bohemia (Czech Republic), and Wackersdorf (Germany). *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 114 (1-2): 83-125. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-6667\(00\)00070-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-6667(00)00070-1)
- KOZŁOWSKA M. & KOZŁOWSKI I. 1984. — *Szczegółowa mapa geologiczna Polski w skali 1:50 000, arkusz Kwidzyn (169)*. Państwowy Instytut Geologiczny, Warszawa.
- KÖTHE A. 1991. — Paleogene dinoflagellates from northwest Germany. *Geologisches Jahrbuch, Reihe A* 118: 1-111.
- KRUTZSCH W. & PACLTOVÁ B. 1990. — Die Phytoplankton – Mikroflora aus den Pliozänen Süßwasserablagerungen des Cheb-Beckens (Westböhmen, ČSFR). *Acta Universitatis Carolinae – Geologica* 4: 345-420.
- KRUTZSCH W., BLUMENSTENGEL H., KIESEL Y. & RÜFFLE L. 1992. — Paläobotanische Klimagliederung des Alttertiärs (Mitteleozän bis Oberoligozän) in Mitteldeutschland und das Problem der Verknüpfung mariner und kontinentaler Gliederungen (klassischer Biostratigraphien – paläobotanisch-ökologische Klimastratigraphie – Evolutions-Stratigraphie der Vertebraten). *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie-Abhandlungen* 186 (1-2): 171-253.
- KUS J., DOLEZYCH M., SCHNEIDER W., HOFMANN T. & VISINÉ RAJČI E. 2020. — Coal petrological and xybotomical characterization of Miocene lignites and *in-situ* fossil tree stumps and trunks from Lusatia region, Germany: palaeoenvironment and taphonomy assessment. *International Journal of Coal Geology* 217: 103283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coal.2019.103283>
- KÜRSCHNER W. M., KVAČEK Z. & DILCHER D. L. 2008. — The impact of Miocene atmospheric carbon dioxide fluctuations on climate and the evolution of terrestrial ecosystems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 105 (2): 449-453. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0708588105>
- KVAČEK Z. 2004. — Revisions to the Early Oligocene flora of Flörsheim (Mainz Basin, Germany) based on epidermal anatomy. *Senckenbergiana lethaea* 84: 1-73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03043465>
- KVAČEK Z. 2007. — Do extant nearest relatives of thermophile European Cenozoic plant elements reliably reflect climatic signal? *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 253 (1-2): 32-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.03.032>
- KVAČEK Z. & WALTHER H. 2001. — The Oligocene of Central Europe and the development of the forest vegetation in space and time based on megafossils. *Palaeontographica, Abteilung B* 259 (1-6): 125-149. <https://doi.org/10.1127/palb/259/2001/125>

- LI S., XING Y., VALDES P. J., HUANG Y., SU T., FARNSWORTH A., LUNT D. J., TANG H., KENNEDY A. T. & ZHOU Z. 2018. — Oligocene climate signals and forcings in Eurasia revealed by plant macrofossil and modelling results. *Gondwana Research* 61: 115-127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gr.2018.04.015>
- LISICKI S. 2010. — *Dokumentacja geologiczna otworu badawczego Grabówka PIG-1 (Grabówka-2)*. Centralne Archiwum Geologiczne Państwowego Instytutu Geologicznego, Warszawa.
- LIU Z., PAGANI M., ZINNIKER D., DECONTO R., HUBER M., BRINKHUIS H., SHAH S. R., LECKIE R. M. & PEARSON A. 2009. — Global cooling during the Eocene-Oligocene climate transition. *Science* 323 (5918): 1187-1190. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1166368>
- LUO C., CHEN M., XIANG R., LIU J., ZHANG L., LU J. & YANG M. 2014. — Modern pollen distribution in marine sediments from the northern part of the South China Sea. *Marine Micropaleontology* 108: 41-56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marmicro.2014.03.001>
- MAI D. H. 1981. — Entwicklung und klimatische Differenzierung der Laubwaldflora Mitteleuropas im Tertiär. *Flora* 171: 525-582. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0367-2530\(17\)31304-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0367-2530(17)31304-X)
- MAI D. H. 1995. — *Tertiäre Vegetationsgeschichte Europas*. Fischer, Jena, 691 p.
- MAI D. H. 1998. — Contribution to the flora of the middle Oligocene Calau Beds in Brandenburg, Germany. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 101 (1-4): 43-70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-6667\(97\)00069-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-6667(97)00069-9)
- MAI D. H. & WALTHER H. 1978. — Die Floren der Haselbacher Serie im Weißelster-Becken (Bezirk Leipzig, DDR). *Abhandlungen des Staatlichen Museums für Mineralogie und Geologie zu Dresden* 28: 1-200.
- MOORE P. D., WEBB J. A. & COLLINSON M. E. 1991. — *Pollen Analysis*. Blackwell, Oxford, 216 p.
- MOSBRUGGER V., GEE C. T., BELZ G. & ASHRAF A. R. 1994. — Three-dimensional reconstruction of an in-situ Miocene peat forest from the Lower Rhine Embayment, northwestern Germany – new methods in palaeovegetation analysis. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 110 (3-4): 295-317. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182\(94\)90089-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182(94)90089-2)
- MOSBRUGGER V., UTESCHER T. & DILCHER D. L. 2005. — Cenozoic continental climatic evolution of Central Europe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 102 (42): 14964-14969. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0505267102>
- MUDIE P. J. 1982. — Pollen distribution in recent marine sediments, eastern Canada. *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences* 19 (4): 729-747. <https://doi.org/10.1139/e82-062>
- NALEPKA D. & WALANUS A. 2003. — Data processing in pollen analysis. *Acta Palaeobotanica* 43: 125-134.
- OBOH F. E. 1992. — Middle Miocene palaeoenvironments of the Niger Delta. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 92 (1-2): 55-84. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182\(92\)90135-R](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182(92)90135-R)
- ODRZYWOLSKA-BIEŃKOWA E., POŻARYSKA K. & MARTINI E. 1978. — Middle Oligocene microfossils from the Polish Lowlands: their stratigraphical and palaeogeographical significance. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 23 (3): 249-291.
- O'BRIEN C. L., HUBER M., THOMAS E., PAGANI M., SUPER J. R., ELDER L. E. & HULL P. M. 2020. — The enigma of Oligocene climate and global surface temperature evolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117 (41): 25302-25309. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2003914117>
- PIWOCKI M. 2004. — Niż Polski i jego południowe obrzeże. Paleogen, in PERYT T. M. & PIWOCKI M. (eds), *Budowa Geologiczna Polski. Stratygrafia. Kenozoik – Paleogen i neogen 1(3a)*. Państwowy Instytut Geologiczny, Warszawa: 22-71.
- POMEROL C. & PREMOLI SILVA I. 1986. — The Eocene-Oligocene transition: events and boundary. *Developments in Palaeontology and Stratigraphy* 9: 1-24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5446\(08\)70090-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5446(08)70090-6)
- PRADER S., KOTTHOFF U., MCCARTHY F. M. G., SCHMIEDL G., DONDERS T. H. & GREENWOOD D. R. 2017. — Vegetation and climate development of the New Jersey hinterland during the late Middle Miocene (IODP Expedition 313 Site M0027). *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 485: 854-868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.07.028>
- PROSS J., BRUCH A. & KVAČEK Z. 1998. — Paläoklima-Rekonstruktionen für den Mittleren Rupelton (Unter-Oligozän) des Mainzer Beckens auf der Basis mikro-und makrobotanischer Befunde. *Mainzer Geowissenschaftliche Mitteilungen* 27: 79-92.
- PROSS J., BRUCH A. A. MOSBRUGGER V. & KVAČEK Z. 2001. — Paleogene pollen and spores as a tool for quantitative paleoclimate reconstructions: the Rupelian (Oligocene) of central Europe, in GOODMAN D. K. & CLARKE R. T. (eds), *Proceedings of the IX International Palynological Congress, Houston, Texas, U.S.A., 1996*. American Association of Stratigraphic Palynologists Foundation: 299-310.
- RICHARDSON C. J. 2003. — Pocosins: hydrologically isolated or integrated wetlands on the landscape? *Wetlands* 23: 563-576. [https://doi.org/10.1672/0277-5212\(2003\)023\[0563:PHIOIW\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1672/0277-5212(2003)023[0563:PHIOIW]2.0.CO;2)
- ROTH-NEBELSICK A., UTESCHER T., MOSBRUGGER V., DIESTERHAASS L. & WALTHER H. 2004. — Changes in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations and climate from the late Eocene to early Miocene; palaeobotanical reconstruction based on fossil floras from Saxony, Germany. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 205 (1-2): 43-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2003.11.014>
- RUOTSALAINEN A. L., KAUPPINEN M., WÄLI P. R., SAIKKONEN K., HELANDER M. & TUOMI J. 2022. — Dark septate endophytes: mutualism from by-products? *Trends in Plant Science* 27 (3): 247-254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2021.10.001>
- SCHNEIDER W. 1992. — Floral successions in Miocene swamps and bogs of Central Europe. *Zeitschrift für Geologische Wissenschaften* 20: 555-570.
- SHACKLETON N. J. & KENNETT J. P. 1975. — Paleotemperature history of the Cenozoic and the initiation of Antarctic Glaciation: oxygen and carbon isotope analyses in DSDP Sites 277, 279 and 281. *Initial Report of the Deep Sea Drilling Project* 29: 743-755. <https://doi.org/10.2973/dsdp.proc.29.117.1975>
- SIEBER T. N. 2002. — Fungal root endophytes, in WASEL Y., ESHEL A. & KAFKAFI U. (eds), *Plant roots: the hidden half*. Marcel Dekker, New York, N.Y.: 887-917.
- SŁODKOWSKA B. 2004a. — Palynological studies of the Paleogene and Neogene deposits from the Pomeranian Lakeland area (NW Poland). *Polish Geological Institute Special Papers* 14: 1-116.
- SŁODKOWSKA B. 2004b. — Tertiary palynological record of the Middle Vistula River valley (central Poland). *Przegląd Geologiczny* 52: 84-86. (in Polish, with English summary).
- SŁODKOWSKA B. 2009. — Palynology of the Palaeogene and Neogene from the Warmia and Mazury areas (NE Poland). *Geologos* 15: 219-234. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10118-009-0005-y>
- STUHLIK L., ZIEMBIŃSKA-TWORZYDŁO M., KOHLMAN-ADAMSKA A., GRABOWSKA I., SŁODKOWSKA B., WAŻYŃSKA H. & SADOWSKA A. 2009. — *Atlas of Pollen and Spores of the Polish Neogene. Volume 3 – Angiosperms (1)*. W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, 233 p.
- STUHLIK L., ZIEMBIŃSKA-TWORZYDŁO M., KOHLMAN-ADAMSKA A., GRABOWSKA I., SŁODKOWSKA B., WOROBIEC E. & DURSKA E. 2014. — *Atlas of Pollen and Spores of the Polish Neogene. Volume 4 – Angiosperms (2)*. W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, 466 p.
- STUHLIK L., ZIEMBIŃSKA-TWORZYDŁO M., KOHLMAN-ADAMSKA A., GRABOWSKA I., WAŻYŃSKA H. & SADOWSKA A. 2002. — *Atlas of Pollen and Spores of the Polish Neogene. Volume 2 – Gymnosperms*. W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, 237 p.

- STUCHLIK L., ZIEMBIŃSKA-TWORZYDŁO M., KOHLMAN-ADAMSKA A., GRABOWSKA I., WAŻYŃSKA H., SŁODKOWSKA B. & SADOWSKA A. 2001. — *Atlas of Pollen and Spores of the Polish Neogene. Volume 1 – Spores*. W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, 158 p.
- ŚLIWIŃSKA K. K. & HEAD M. 2020. — New species of the dinoflagellate cyst genus *Svalbardella* Manum, 1960, emend. from the Paleogene and Neogene of the northern high to middle latitudes. *Journal of Micropalaeontology* 39 (2): 139-154. <https://doi.org/10.5194/jm-39-139-2020>
- ŚLIWIŃSKA K. K. & HEILMANN-CLAUSEN C. 2011. — Early Oligocene cooling reflected by the dinoflagellate cyst *Svalbardella cooksoniae*. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 305 (1-4): 138-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2011.02.027>
- ŚLIWIŃSKA K. K., THOMSEN E., SCHOUTEN S., SCHOON P. L. & HEILMANN-CLAUSEN C. 2019. — Climate- and gateway-driven cooling of Late Eocene to earliest Oligocene sea surface temperatures in the North Sea Basin. *Scientific Reports* 9: 4458. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41013-7>
- TRAVERSE A. 2007. — Differential Sorting of Palynomorphs into Sediments: Palynofacies, Palynodebris, Discordant Palynomorphs, in MYERSKATHLEEN C. & RITTERBUSH A. (eds), *Paleopalynology. Topics in Geobiology*. Vol. 28. Springer, Dordrecht: 543-579. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5610-9_18
- TYSON R. V. 1995. — *Sedimentary Organic Matter: Organic Facies and Palynofacies*. Chapman & Hall, London, 615 p. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-0739-6>
- UTESCHER T. & MOSBRUGGER V. 2015. — *The Palaeoflora Database*. <http://www.palaeoflora.de/> (last accessed on December 2022).
- UTESCHER T., BRUCH A. A. & MOSBRUGGER V. 2024. — The Palaeoflora Database - Documentation and Data (Version 2024) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10881069>
- UTESCHER T., BRUCH A. A., ERDEI B., FRANÇOIS L., IVANOV D., JACQUES F. M. B., KERN A. K., LIU Y-S.(C.), MOSBRUGGER V. & SPICER R. A. 2014. — The coexistence approach – theoretical background and practical considerations of using plant fossils for climate quantification. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 410: 58-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2014.05.031>
- UTESCHER T., ERDEI B., FRANÇOIS L., HENROT A.-J., MOSBRUGGER V. & POPOVA S. 2021. — Oligocene vegetation of Europe and western Asia – Diversity change and continental patterns reflected by plant functional types. *Geological Journal* 56 (2): 628-649. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gj.3830>
- VAN DER KAARS S. 2001. — Pollen distribution in marine sediments from the south-eastern Indonesian waters. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 171 (3-4): 341-361. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182\(01\)00253-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182(01)00253-X)
- VAN GEEL B. & GRENFELL H. R. 1996. — Chapter 7A. Spores of Zygnemataceae, in JANSONIUS J. & MCGREGOR D. C. (eds), *Palynology: Principles and Applications*. 1. American Association of Stratigraphic Palynologists Foundation: 173-179.
- VAN SIMAEYS S., BRINKHUIS H., PROSS J., WILLIAMS G. L. & ZACHOS J. C. 2005. — Arctic dinoflagellate migrations mark the strongest Oligocene glaciations. *Geology* 33 (9): 709-712. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G21634.1>
- VAN WAVEREN I. M. 1989. — Pattern analysis of organic component abundances from deltaic and open marine deposits: palynofacies distribution (East Java, Indonesia). *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research* 23 (4): 441-447. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0077-7579\(89\)90027-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0077-7579(89)90027-6)
- VINKEN R. (ED.) 1988. — The Northwest European Tertiary basin, results of the international geological correlation programme, project no. 124. *Geologisches Jahrbuch, Reihe A* 100: 1-508.
- WALTHER H. & KVAČEK Z. 2007. — Early Oligocene flora of Seiffenhennersdorf (Saxony). *Acta Musei Nationalis Pragae, Serie B - Historia Naturalis* 63 (2-4): 85-174.
- WESTERHOLD T., MARWAN N., DRURY A. J., LIEBRAND D., AGNINI C., ANAGNOSTOU E., BARNET J. S. K., BOHATY S. M., DE VLEESCHOUWER D., FLORINDO F., FREDERICH S. T., HODELL D. A., HOLBOURN A. E., KROON D., LAURETANO V., LITTLER K., LOURENS L. J., LYLE M., PÁLÍKE H., RÖHL U., TIAN J., WILKENS R. H., WILSON P. A. & ZACHOS J. C. 2020. — An astronomically dated record of Earth's climate and its predictability over the last 66 million years. *Science* 369 (6509): 1383-1387. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba6853>
- WIDERA M. 2016. — Genetic classification of Polish lignite deposits: A review. *International Journal of Coal Geology* 158: 107-118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coal.2016.03.004>
- WIDERA M. & KITA A. 2007. — Paleogene marginal marine sedimentation in central-western Poland. *Geological Quarterly* 51: 79-90.
- WOROBIEC E. 2010. — Late Miocene freshwater phytoplankton from Józefina (Poland). *Micropaleontology* 56 (6): 517-537. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40983739>
- WOROBIEC E. 2011. — Middle Miocene aquatic and wetland vegetation of the paleosinkhole at Tarnów Opolski, SW Poland. *Journal of Paleolimnology* 45: 311-322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10933-011-9499-8>
- WOROBIEC E. 2014. — Fossil zygospores of Zygnemataceae and other microremains of freshwater algae from two Miocene palaeosinkholes in the Opole region, SW Poland. *Acta Palaeobotanica* 54 (1): 113-157. <https://doi.org/10.2478/acpa-2014-0005>
- WOROBIEC E. & SZULC J. 2020. — Palynology of Oligocene lignites in two karst palaeosinkholes at Góraźdze, Upper Silesia, Poland. *Annales Societatis Geologorum Poloniae* 90 (4): 495-504. <https://doi.org/10.14241/asgp.2020.26>
- WOROBIEC E., WIDERA M., WOROBIEC G. & KURDZIEL B. 2021. — Middle Miocene palynoflora from the Adamów lignite deposit, central Poland. *Palynology* 45 (1): 59-71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01916122.2019.1697388>
- ZACHOS J., PAGANI M., SLOAN L., THOMAS E. & BILLUPS K. 2001. — Trends, rhythms, and aberrations in global climate 65 Ma to present. *Science* 292 (5517): 686-693. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1059412>
- ZACHOS J. C., DICKENS G. R. & ZEEBE R. E. 2008. — An Early Cenozoic perspective on greenhouse warming and carbon-cycle dynamics. *Nature* 451: 279-283. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06588>
- ZIPPI P. A. 1998. — Freshwater algae from the Mattagami Formation (Albian), Ontario: paleoecology, botanical affinities, and systematic taxonomy. *Micropaleontology* 44 (1): 1-78. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1485998>
- ZONNEVELD, K. A. F., MARRET F., VERSTEEGH G. J. M., BOGUS K., BONNET S., BOUIMETARHAN I., CROUCH E., DE VERNAL A., ELSHANAWANY R., EDWARDS L., ESPER O., FORKE S., GRØSFJELD K., HENRY M., HOLZWARHTH U., KIELT J.-F., KIM S. Y., LADOUCEUR S., LEDU D., CHEN L., LIMOGES A., LONDEIX L., LU S.-H., MAHMOUD M. S., MARINO G., MATSUOKA K., MATTHIENSEN J., MILDENHAL D. C., MUDIE P., NEIL H. L., POSPELOVA V., QI Y., RADI T., RICHEROL T., ROCHON A., SANGIORGI F., SOLIGNAC S., TURON J.-L., VERLEYE T., WANG Y., WANG Z. & YOUNG M. 2013. — Atlas of modern dinoflagellate cyst distribution based on 2405 data points. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 191: 1-197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revpalbo.2012.08.003>

Submitted on 11 December 2023;
accepted on 7 November 2024;
published on 5 March 2025.